

D1.1: STATE OF THE ART, GAPS AND CHALLENGES FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT MARITIME PORTS

PROJECT ID: Project 101147041 — CLARION

CLARION WEBSITE: <https://projectclarion.eu/>

Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)

© CLARION Project 2024

Reproduction is authorised, provided the source is acknowledged, save where otherwise stated.

Project data

Document	
Grant agreement n°	101147041
Acronym	CLARION
Project title	Climate Resilient Port Infrastructure
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01-09
Start date	1 st May 2024
End date	30 th April 2028
Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://projectclarion.eu/

Document Info

Deliverable	
Document reference	D1.1 State of the Art, Gaps and Challenges for Climate Resilient Maritime Ports
Due Date of Delivery to EC	31-08-2024
Actual Date of Delivery to EC	30-08-2024
Document type	R
Dissemination level	Public
Work package	WP1 Climate effects assessment and adaptation planning
Lead beneficiary	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutou Systematon Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston
Reviewers' Organisation	Technische Universiteit Delft

Author(s) & contributors	
Author(s)	Anastasia Roukouni and Sofia Kokonezi (ICCS)
Organizations	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston
Main Contributor(s) (alphabetical order)	Alfred Roubos (POR) Benjamin Blanck (HPA) Carlos Martin-Portugues Montoliu (ACCIONA) Cristiana Dima (MPAC) Geert Potters (HZS) Georgios Sarigiannis (INLECOM) Johan Gille (POR) Luca Flessati (TUD) Mario Bačić (RESDEV) Nadia Pourmohammadzia (TUD) Stefaan Ides (POAB) Thomas Bles (DELTARES) Victor Castelot (RESAL)

Revision history			
Version	Date	Organisation	Summary of Modifications
V0.1	17-06-2024	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston	ToC circulation
V0.2	05-07-2024	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston	Consolidation of input
V0.3	30-07-2024	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston	Internal review
V0.4	02-08-2024	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston	Sent to Coordinator
V0.5	26-08-2024	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston	Ready for submission
V1.0	30-08-2024	Technische Universiteit Delft	Final version

Quality control			
Reviewer	Role	Organisation	Approval date
Benjamin Blanck	WP Leader	Hamburg Port Authority	19-08-2024
Ken Gavin	Scientific Project Coordinator	Technische Universiteit Delft	30-08-2024
Danitsja van Heusden	Project Coordinator	Technische Universiteit Delft	30-08-2024

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union (EU) or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Acronyms and Abbreviations	
Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADIF	Administrador de Infraestructuras Ferroviarias
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
AoN	All-or-Nothing
API	Application Programming Interface
BAU	Business as Usual
BRO	Beneficial Reuse Option
CBA	Cost-Benefit analysis
CDF	Confined Disposal Facility
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CONRO	Container / Roll on-Roll off vessel.
CoSMoS	Coastal Storm Modelling System
DT	Digital Twin
EMS	Emergency Management System
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
HPA	Hamburg Port Authority
INA	Institutional Network Analysis
IoT	Internet of Things
IWT	Inland Water Transport
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MATSim	Multi-Agent Transport Simulation
MS	Modal Split
NBS	Natural Based Solutions
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PCB	Polychlorinated biphenyl(s)
PERS	Port Environmental Review System
PHA	Polyhydroxy Acid(s)
PI	Physical Internet
PoR	Port of Rotterdam

Acronyms and Abbreviations	
Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
RDM	Rotterdamsche Droogdok Maatschappij
RORO	Roll on / Roll off vessel
RSM	Response Surface Methods
SDM	Self Diagnosis Method
SHFM	Structural Health and Functionality Monitoring
SLR	Sea Level Rise
SO	System Optimum
TEU	Twenty-foot Equivalent Units
UE	User Equilibrium

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	9
1.1. Methodology	9
2. Towards Europe’s Green Ports	10
2.1. Vision towards Europe’s Green Ports	10
2.2. Setting the Scene	11
3. State of the Art	12
3.1. State-of-the-Art in infrastructure resilience and safety in maritime ports	12
3.2. State-of-the-Art in transport resilience and safety in maritime ports	15
4. European Ports’ current practices	19
4.1. Port infrastructure resilience and safety in maritime ports	19
4.1.1. Quay walls	19
4.1.2. Corrosion of port infrastructure	19
4.1.3. Shore tension for RO/RO and CON/RO terminals	22
4.1.4. Flood impact control	22
4.1.5. Dredged sediment reuse	24
4.1.6. Nature Based Solutions for maritime ports	27
4.2. Transport resilience and safety in maritime ports	33
4.2.1. Resilience of connected inland waterways, roads and railways infrastructure	33
4.2.2. Extreme weather forecasting	36
4.2.3. Cadastral measurements and inland water level forecasting	37
4.2.4. EMS for extreme weather events	38
4.3. Best practices outside the EU	39
5. Existing Initiatives & Collaborative Communities	41
5.1. International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH)	41
5.2. European Sea Ports Organisation (ESPO)	41
5.3. International Port Community Systems Association (IPCSA)	42
5.4. Green Ports Forum	42
5.5. WATERBORNE	42
5.6. chainPORT	43
5.7. Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE)	43
5.8. SedNeT	43
5.9. Central Dredging Association (CEDA)	44

5.10.	World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC)	44
5.11.	International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR)	44
5.12.	European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)	44
6.	Related research projects	46
7.	Key findings from the stakeholders' interviews	51
8.	Conclusion	54
9.	Annexes	55
Annex 1		55
Annex 2		60
Annex 3		66

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: REEF BALL (SOURCE: REEF BALL FOUNDATION, 2024) ¹³⁶	27
FIGURE 2: IMPRESSION OF A LANDSCAPE DYKE	28
FIGURE 3: 2030 PORT VISION. PORT OF ROTTERDAM (SOURCE: POR, 2023) ¹³⁹	29
FIGURE 4: NATIVE OYSTERS IN THE POR (SOURCE: NORA, 2020) ¹⁴⁰	30
FIGURE 5: ECOBLOCKS FROM ECONCRETE (LEFT) AND LEGO BLOCKS DEPLOYED AS PART OF THE ROTTERDAM REEF (RIGHT)	30
FIGURE 6: FLOATING STRUCTURE TO PROMOTE BIODIVERSITY IN THE PORT OF ROTTERDAM	31
FIGURE 7: IMPRESSION OF THE MALLEGATPARK TIDAL PARK DURING LOW TIDE (TOP) AND HIGH TIDE (BOTTOM) (SOURCE: VAN DEN BERG, 2018, IMAGE FROM THE MUNICIPALITY OF ROTTERDAM)	31
FIGURE 8: SLUFTER: CONFINED DISPOSAL FACILITY	32
FIGURE 9: LINK BETWEEN THE NBS AND THE DIGITAL MONITORING (SOURCE: ECOSHAPE, 2021 ¹⁴³)	33

List of Tables

TABLE 1: EFFECTIVENESS OF NBS ON COASTAL APPLICATIONS(SOURCES: FERRARIO ET AL., 2014; DEBELE ET AL., 2019; , NARAYAN ET AL., 2016)	14
TABLE 2: CALCULATION OF ESTIMATED CORROSION COST FOR FOUR OF THE CLARION PORTS.	20
TABLE 3: RESEARCH PROJECTS RELEVANT TO CLARION	50
TABLE A1: OVERVIEW OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH (OF THE LAST 5 YEARS: 2019-2024) IN THE FIELD OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND PORTS	55
TABLE B1: EXISTING WORK ON RESILIENCE OF CONNECTED INLAND WATERWAYS, ROADS AND RAILWAYS INFRASTRUCTURE	60

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable report is the result of the research and analysis performed in the context of the CLARION WP1, task T.1.1., “Definition of the current SotA and innovation drivers”. The report presents a thorough overview of the state-of-the-art in port climate resilience, highlighting best-practices as well as key challenges, and identifying potential gaps in existing approaches. It also includes a comprehensive and up-to-date inventory of emerging trends and innovation drivers for improving climate resiliency in maritime ports. The employed methodology is a combination of desk research and interviews with key port stakeholders. Initially, the state-of-the-art is presented, including the most innovative and advanced research available on the field of port infrastructure and transport resilience and safety. Following that, the state-of-the-practice focuses more on practical applications, case studies and real-world scenarios, diving into specific practices adopted by European ports to enhance resilience. This part is divided into ten focus areas, each one being relevant to one of the ten CLARION pilots. Best practices in port resilience outside the EU are also included in the report, as successful initiatives applied elsewhere can be potentially interesting for European ports. The identification of existing initiatives and collaborative communities that are driving the development of green and resilient port infrastructure follows, as well as a review of existing relevant research projects. Key findings from a survey conducted among stakeholders, provide additional valuable insights into the current climate-related challenges and opportunities in different European ports. The report concludes with highlighting important points to be taken into account when planning for climate port resilience and safety.

1.1. Methodology

The methodology followed for CLARION deliverable D1.1 comprises desk research and a number of semi-structured and unstructured interviews with key port experts, actors and stakeholders. Initially, a thorough and comprehensive literature review of the state-of-the-art and the state-of-the-practice regarding port resilience and safety in the EU and beyond was performed. Scientific literature has been reviewed, as well as so-called grey literature - reports, white papers, news articles, blogs, and websites. Key words and phrases in different combinations were used for the online search, such as “climate change”, “hazards”, “impact”, “(green) ports”, “resilience”, “safety”, “sustainability”, “innovation”, and the snowball method was also employed to enrich the search results. Moreover, the CLARION partners involved in the ten pilot demonstrations of the project were asked to contribute to the report with their knowledge and experience on existing research, projects, case studies and/or other port initiatives relevant to their pilots or to any other component of the report. In addition to that, interviews with stakeholders from different ports were conducted, either by online discussions or by e-mail, using as a basis a list of ten indicative questions that was shared with them. The stakeholders discussed how climate change is affecting the port they are associated with, and what actions are currently taken to make sure the port is part of the transition to more sustainable, resilient, green, safe, and future-proof ports.

2. Towards Europe's Green Ports

2.1. Vision towards Europe's Green Ports

Maritime ports play an unambiguously critical role in global supply chains, with the goods' volume transported worldwide by sea reaching a remarkable 90% of global trade (ICS, 2024)¹. Due to their strategic locations, ports are exposed to natural hazards and are experiencing the growing impacts of climate change that can cause damage to port infrastructure and directly affect their operations (Yang and Ge, 2020)². These impacts include among others; Sea Level Rise (SLR) (Jebbad et al., 2022)³, intense storms and storm surge (Ribeiro et al., 2023⁴; Cid et al., 2015⁵), flooding (Becker and Inoue, 2012)⁶, changes in wave patterns (Sierra et al., 2017)⁷, extreme weather events such as hurricanes/cyclones/typhoons or heatwaves (Diffenbaugh et al., 2017)⁸. In case of extreme weather events, ports act as the first line of defence and safety for coastal areas and cities, being the ones that are hit first (Deloitte and ESPO, 2021)⁹. According to a recently published (2023) research study conducted by the Environmental Change Institute of the University of Oxford, which investigated potential climate risks for 1,340 ports all over the world, the great majority of them (86%) is exposed to at least three different climate hazards (Verschuur et al., 2023)¹⁰. For an overview of key scientific literature of the last five years (2019-2024) in the field of climate change and ports, see Table A 1 of Annex 1.

Enhancing proactively the climate resilience of port infrastructure and operations, emerges therefore as a key element in ensuring that ports will be able to continue thriving and being the backbone of global supply chains and the economy in the years to come (Liu et al., 2024)¹¹. As places where people, goods, and different transport modes meet, ports are at the forefront of the transition towards a more sustainable future. Many ports around the world are increasingly adopting environmentally friendly approaches and embracing novel technologies to reduce their ecological footprint, following what has become widely known as "green port" initiatives (Philipp et al., 2021)¹². The European Green Deal leaves no room for misinterpretation; in order to succeed in achieving the goal of zero-net emissions by 2050 (EC, 2019)¹³, European ports have to engage in more and more green practices, covering every component of their complex ecosystems; from infrastructure maintenance to hinterland transport and operations. Information sharing and increased communication, transparency and collaboration among policy makers and stakeholders in port communities, can make planning for resilience more effective (Becker et al., 2012)¹⁴, as the process of "greening" should not only entail the reduction of negative externalities, but also the alignment of objectives, agendas and aspirations towards the common goal of both mitigating and adapting to climate change (Deloitte and ESPO, 2021)⁹.

¹ <https://www.ics-shipping.org/shipping-fact/shipping-and-world-trade-global-supply-and-demand-for-seafarers/>

² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2020.06.019>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2021.102623>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11030477>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-015-2659-1>

⁶ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10584-011-0043-7>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2017.06.002>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1618082114>

⁹ https://www.espo.be/media/Deloitte-ESPO%20study%20-%20Europe%20transitions_1.pdf

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00656-7>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1080/03088839.2024.2367971>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.2478/rtuct-2021-0049>

¹³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0043-7>

In addition to the climate – related external disruptions described above, ports are subject to pandemics such as COVID-19 (ITF, 2024)¹⁵, as well as geopolitical conflicts that can disrupt global supply networks (UNCTAD, 2022)¹⁶. Moreover, terrorism, cyber-attacks (Senarak, 2023)¹⁷, and other security concerns can pose further safety risks.

2.2. Setting the Scene

As maritime ports need to navigate these multifaceted challenges, investing in the long-term resilience and safety of infrastructure and operations becomes increasingly important. In order to be able to comply with EU's strategic vision to reduce drastically greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and at the same time continue to be prosperous centres of economic activity for the years to come, European ports should not only adopt environmentally friendly practices but also aim at enhancing their ability to face adverse events and recover successfully from them. In this context, the objective of this report is to provide a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art in port climate resilience, highlight best-practices as well as common challenges, and identify potential gaps in existing approaches.

¹⁵ <https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/transport-system-resilience.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://resilientmaritimelogistics.unctad.org/guidebook/16-geopolitical-events>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41278-023-00276-8>

3. State of the Art

3.1. State-of-the-Art in infrastructure resilience and safety in maritime ports

As discussed in Section 2.1, maritime port infrastructure is exposed to various climate hazards, and this can affect several components of it. In an era of rapid technological process, and with ports often acting as incubators of innovation (see e.g. the Rotterdamsche Droogdok Maatschappij (RDM) area¹⁸ within the Port of Rotterdam), there is a wide variety of novel methods, techniques and tools that are being developed to help enhancing the infrastructure resilience and safety in seaports all over the world. These can include, among others, introducing smart digital components to quay walls, addressing steel corrosion, improving mooring conditions, developing effective flood impact control systems, reusing dredged sediments and experimenting with nature-based solutions.

Quay walls play a critical role in enabling the smooth operation and in safeguarding ports and coastal areas in general, as they deal with increased pressure from extreme weather events and sea level rise that accelerates degradation. The most common materials used to build quay walls are steel and concrete, leading to high GHG emissions as well as high costs (Schmidt and Van Rouwendaal, 2022)¹⁹. To limit the environmental impact of developing and maintaining quay walls, new approaches and techniques can be used, in an attempt to make them smart and sustainable such as installing sensors on them and use drones and remote sensing to collect information on when maintenance or replacement is necessary, or opting for sustainable construction materials and green infrastructure such as floating gardens to absorb and filter rainwater (Deltares, 2024)²⁰.

One of the major reasons of deterioration of port infrastructure is the process of steel corrosion, an often-underestimated threat to other sectors of the economy, as well; it is met not only at ports, but in any kind of industry where water meets steel such as the whole maritime sector, water purification plants, energy production and offshore (renewable) energy production. It has been estimated that approximately 5 tons of steel per second are lost through corrosion (Ramos et al., 2023)²¹. Coastal infrastructure decay is accelerated by climate change, as high temperatures and humidity can amplify steel corrosion (Zhang et al., 2022)²². The costs pertaining to corrosion are immense: the IMPACT study (NACE, 2016)²³ sets all-round annual corrosion costs to an estimated US\$2.5 trillion, which corresponds to 3.4% of the global gross domestic product (GDP) (2013). The EU's GDP at market prices was €14.5 trillion in 2021 (Eurostat, 2023), which – following the methodology and the global estimate of the IMPACT study mentioned above – leads to an estimate of a corrosion cost of about €552 billion. In the Oil and Gas Industry (North Sea production platforms), 60% of all maintenance costs, according to a 1993 study, are, directly or indirectly, related to corrosion (Obot et al., 2020)²⁴, and so are 90% of ship failures (Melchers, 1999)²⁵.

A recent study (2022) published in Nature²⁴, highlights the importance of employing corrosion management best-practices to limit the GHG emissions that result from the replacement of corroded steel; replacing a ton of corroding steel produces 1.6 ton of CO₂. Corrosion is therefore responsible for 1.3-2.5%

¹⁸ <https://rotterdammakeithappen.nl/en/showcases/rdm-rotterdam-source-of-innovation/>

¹⁹ <https://www.iadc-dredging.com/article/reinforced-soil-quay-wall-structure/>

²⁰ <https://www.deltares.nl/en/expertise/areas-of-expertise/future-proof-infrastructure/quay-walls-smart-and-future-proof>

²¹ Ramos Giani, van Geffen Gerrit, Van Horebeek Ruben (2023) Corrosieanalyse van S355, S235 en 316L staal in een havenomgeving. Master dissertation, Antwerp Maritime Academy.

²² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcns.2022.04.004>

²³ <http://impact.nace.org/documents/Nace-International-Report.pdf>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2019.106469>

²⁵ [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X\(99\)00010-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X(99)00010-3)

of the GHG emissions of the EU, and under the goals of the Green Deal, this will amount to 3.9-7.6% of all GHG emissions (calculated according to Iannuzzi and Frankel, 2022²⁶). Corrosion management best practices can include corrosion resistant designs, proper coating maintenance, cathodic protection (Pailes, 2022)²⁷, corrosion life-cycle management (Zen, 2005)²⁸ or using response surface methods (RSM) and artificial neural networks (ANN) to predict corrosion (Kumari and Lavanya, 2024)²⁹.

Due to economies of scale, the size of seagoing vessels has increased tremendously in the last decades (Cullinane and Khanna, 2000)³⁰. While this increase in vessel dimensions has had an effect on the manoeuvrability of sailing vessels in ports, it also impacts the behaviour of moored vessels in a port, as the windage area of the vessels increases together with the vessel size (Grlj et al., 2023)³¹. Some vessels, such as container, RORO, CONRO and cruise vessels, are vulnerable to wind due to their large windage area. Since the occurrence and intensity of severe storms are increasing due to climate change, it becomes a challenge to keep those vessels safely moored during such conditions. If the wind load on such a vessel becomes too high, the mooring lines will roll off the winch or even break and the vessel will come adrift. (Ricci et al., 2020)³². This poses a dangerous situation for both the vessel itself and any vessel in its proximity, as well as for the port infrastructure.

A classic approach to tackle such storm conditions is to use storm bollards (Broos et al., 2018)³³. face of the quay wall, which offer an ideal configuration for very efficient breast These are bollards which are ca. 30m away from the vertical lines. However, this solution is only possible at dedicated terminals where the mooring lines running over the terminal do not bother (typically for a tank terminal). Another solution is the use of tug boats during storm conditions. These tug boats will come aside the moored vessel and start pushing the vessel against the quay wall (Paulauskas et al., 2021)³⁴. This is not a sustainable solution though, since the tugs are using fuel during the entire storm period and are not available for regular tug services at that time.

Flooding due to SLR and storm surges could have both temporary and permanent effects to seaports. More than 60% of all seaports worldwide are expected to be inundated according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2012)³⁵ due to the rise of global mean sea levels and the combined effects of tides, local waves, and storm surges and the number of ports expected to be exposed to inundation levels higher than 1 m is estimated to grow by 80% between 2030 and 2080 (Christodoulou et al., 2019)³⁶. By 2100, it is estimated that 83% of ports could face extreme sea levels exceeding 2 m (Asariotis et al., 2024)³⁷.

Sedimentation is the natural process where elements settle at the bottom of water bodies, such as rivers, lakes, and harbours. Over time, this accumulation can obstruct waterways, impede navigation, and affect aquatic ecosystems. To address these issues, dredging is performed to remove the excess sediment and maintain the desired water depth. Europe-wide, the volume of dredged material is very roughly estimated

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41529-022-00318-1>

²⁷ <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/10.1061/9780784484395.073>

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2005.04.003>

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40735-024-00863-z>

³⁰ [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6923\(00\)00010-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0966-6923(00)00010-7)

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.113991>

³² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2020.104315>

³³

https://pure.tudelft.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/51686300/Position_paper_bollard_loads_on_port_infrastructure_PIANC_final.pdf

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3390/imse9030342>

³⁵ <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/managing-the-risks-of-extreme-events-and-disasters-to-advance-climate-change-adaptation/>

³⁶ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/s41278-018-0114-z>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44218-024-00047-9>

at 200 million m³ per year (SedNet, 2004)³⁸. Traditionally, dredged material was often disposed of as waste, potentially harming the environment and the ecosystems. However, dredged sediment can be repurposed in various beneficial ways, such as restoring wetlands, replenishing eroded coastlines, flood control and improving soil quality for agriculture.

Coastal protection usually relies on ‘hard’ engineering solutions that are unlikely to withstand the increasing pressure from intensified hydrometeorological hazards caused by climate change (Kumar et al., 2020)³⁹. Moreover, the maintenance costs of such structures could become unfeasible (Morris et al., 2018)⁴⁰, so a universal “hold the line” coastal management or protection policy in the face of increasing climate pressures can be unsustainable. Therefore, the need of lower cost, sustainable and resilient solutions is increasing. In this context, Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are emerging globally as a strategy that employ natural features to address hazards while enhancing biodiversity (EC, 2022)⁴¹. The European Commission through The EU Research and Innovation policy agenda on Nature-based Solutions and Re-naturing Cities, defines Nature-based Solutions as: *“Solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions.* It further emphasizes that “NBS must benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services.”⁴¹

The implementation of NbS is supported by different European policies, such as The Green Infrastructure Strategy, the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change and the Floods Directive. Typical examples of NbS include mudflats, dunes, beach nourishment and coral reefs. According to the independent expert report “Nature-based solutions, State of the art in EU-funded projects” (Bulkeley et al., 2020)⁴², each NbS type requires certain conditions in order to be effective. The report also mentions that coastal habitats can reduce wave heights between 35% and 71%⁴³, and that restoration projects in mangroves and salt marshes for wave reduction can be several times cheaper than alternative such as breakwaters, for the same level of protection. They are also able to self-repair after strong storms and have much lower maintenance costs than artificial infrastructures^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}. The following table (Table 1) summarises the effectiveness of NbS interventions for coastal applications.

NbS	Effectiveness	
	Runoff volume reduction	Peak flow reduction
Coral Reefs	-70-91%	-34-3200%
Salt Marshes	-72-92%	-5-425%
Mangroves	-31-53%	-32-260%
Seagrass	-36-58%	-258-949%

Table 1: Effectiveness of NbS on Coastal applications⁴² (Sources: Ferrario et al., 2014;⁴⁴ Debele et al., 2019; ⁴⁵ Narayan et al., 2016⁴⁶)

³⁸ https://sednet.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Sednet_booklet_final_2.pdf

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138855>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14063>

⁴¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/environment/nature-based-solutions_en.

⁴² <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/236007>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms4794>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108799>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0154735>

Other approaches towards resiliency and safety in port infrastructure can include hybrid green-grey infrastructure, Artificial Intelligence (AI) for predictive analysis and for surveillance of water levels (Graham, 2024)⁴⁷.

3.2. State-of-the-Art in transport resilience and safety in maritime ports

In port environments, many different modes of transport meet and co-exist, therefore multimodality is a key in working towards hinterland transport resilience and safety. Another critical topic is forecasting and managing extreme weather events, and in ports that have inland water connections, an important step towards enhancing resilience is to perform forecasting of inland water levels. The combination of cutting-edge technology, collaborative frameworks, and adaptive approaches meant to improve the robustness and security of port operations, defines the current level of transport resilience and safety in maritime ports. Key improvements include the use of digital twins and automated systems for real-time modelling and analysis of port activities, which allows for proactive decision-making and quick response to disruptions. This feature enables ports to better predict and mitigate the effects of unforeseen events, greatly increasing resilience.

Furthermore, the integration of Internet of Thing (IoT) devices and AI-powered analytics (Xu et al., 2023)⁴⁸ allows for continuous monitoring of infrastructure health and operational efficiency, minimising risks and assuring more dependable operations. These technological advancements are reinforced by collaborative frameworks that promote information sharing and coordinated actions among stakeholders, which are critical for controlling disruptions that have cascading impacts across linked global transportation networks. Joint resilience drills, emergency response procedures, and integrated initiatives that combine physical infrastructure improvements with legislative measures emphasise a comprehensive approach to promoting a robust and safe marine transport sector.

Starting from providing an overview of multimodal transport resilience, Serdar et al. (2022)⁴⁹ introduce an evaluation of resilience methods for transportation networks along with their corresponding indicators. The study classifies the methods used into big-data driven, simulation-based, optimisation, graph theory (network topology), and probabilistic-based approaches. Another comprehensive resilience study (Xu and Chopra, 2023)⁵⁰, investigates the interconnectedness among various transport systems, employing a topological approach. The topological model, due to its ability to encapsulate the essence of network-like infrastructures (such as the linkage of different locations inherent to transportation systems), has become a favoured method for transportation system analysis. The study introduces three indicators based on the “safe-to-fail” concept (from the resilience-by-design perspective), namely preparedness, robustness, and interoperability. These indicators are designed to assess whether the network topology is well-structured to manage the failure of any single component, to preserve essential functionality during progressive failures to a significant degree, and to interoperate with the remaining components to temporarily sustain functionality.

With regard to transport systems’ robustness, He et al. (2021)⁵¹ introduce a method for network modelling and robustness evaluation for multimodal freight transport networks. ‘Robustness’ is understood as the ability of a transport network to avoid direct and indirect economic losses. It is defined by the extent to

⁴⁷ <https://blog.ehab.co/coastal-management-innovations-future-ready-port-resilience>

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11122311>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.103452>

⁵⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39999-w>

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2020.107315>

which the transport network can operate in the face of various capacity disruptions on transport elements. In the proposed model in this research, nodes symbolise terminals and crossings, while links denote pathways. The model encapsulates the characteristics of interconnection and interdependency. Perturbations, such as disruptions of infrastructure elements and capacity degradation of pathways, are considered. The robustness of the network is assessed based on the increase in total travel time caused by these perturbations. This robustness evaluation model is applied to Dutch freight transport, considering three modes of transport: inland waterways, roads, railways, and transshipment terminals. To derive travel time, practical traffic assignments, including all-or-nothing (AoN) assignments, modal split (MS), user equilibrium (UE), and system optimum (SO), are implemented as part of the robustness assessment of multimodal freight transport networks.

Achilopoulou et al. (2020)⁵² propose a method to enhance the transport network resilience by supporting emergency rescue decisions in defining the location selection strategies of rescue facilities. This research presents a strategic plan to establish a connection between the elements of multi-hazard resilience evaluation in transport infrastructure. This connection is based on a diverse range of Structural Health and Functionality Monitoring (SHFM) data, which is combined with models to provide actionable performance indicators and diagnosis. In this way, the potential of sensory data can be harnessed to aid in predicting the condition of the asset and the functionality of the network. Consequently, risk can be assessed efficiently, almost instantaneously with high precision, with the goal of maximising functionality and minimising losses. This approach is particularly relevant in the context of monitoring transport infrastructure exposed to multiple hazards, as it contributes to building resilience.

Despite the increasing focus on the domain of multimodal resilience in academic literature, the prevailing trend in research and tool development is to primarily concentrate on evaluating the resilience of individual modes of transport. The following examples present such cases.

Van Ginkel et al. (2022)⁵³ evaluated the resilience of European countries' road networks and their susceptibility to a tipping point, defined as a sudden and disproportionately large loss of network functionality due to adverse flood combinations. The methodology is influenced by percolation analysis, with tens of thousands of flood combinations sampled and their impacts on road network performance evaluated. The findings indicate that Albania, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria are relatively susceptible, while Belgium, Estonia, Lithuania, and Portugal demonstrate relative robustness. While the likelihood of nationwide network fragmentation appears low, the occurrence of regional-scale tipping points is plausible. Strengthening the identified vulnerabilities could provide immediate benefits for national road operators. While percolation methods effectively measure the impact on road networks, they offer minimal insight into the effects on travel and transport functionality. Therefore, Rajput et al. (2023)⁵⁴ aimed to uncover the structure of disrupted traffic networks by utilising high-resolution traffic network data from a significant flood event and sophisticated high-order network analysis. This study calculates travel times between each pair of junctions in the city and examines changes in higher-order network geometry to ascertain flood impacts. The results of this research offer a novel and crucial understanding of the effects of floods on the operation of traffic networks in terms of travel time and traffic network geometry.

Yadav et al. (2020)⁵⁵ introduced a comprehensive computational framework for quantitatively comprehending resilience, encompassing robustness and recovery, of real-world and spatially restricted network-of-networks of urban railways in London. The study employs a hypothesis-driven approach to

⁵² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141001>

⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2022.103332>

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.104693>

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-66049-y>

manage the intricacies of spatial network-of-networks, leading to universal theories for resilience. The study discovers that topological characteristics, which are designed to enhance efficiency rather than robustness, make the network more susceptible to complex natural-targeted disruptions, including cascading failures. The findings imply that a guiding principle for recovery post-disruption could be established using network science principles. The loss of functionality during the disruption phase is depicted by the size of the network-of-network, while the functionality regained during recovery is represented by the additional alterations in the shortest paths among nodes, traffic demand, and restoration costs.

In terms of multi-modal transport adaptation modelling, Sun et al. (2020)⁵⁶ introduce a comprehensive plan that encompasses various coastal defence measures in response to a predicted one-meter rise in sea level by 2100. The approach integrates high-definition hydrodynamic simulations via the Coastal Storm Modelling System (CoSMoS) and traffic simulations through the Multi-Agent Transport Simulation (MATSim). These tools are used to assess the potential repercussions of sea level rise and mitigation strategies on both the highway and public transit systems in the San Francisco Bay Area. By incorporating public transit into the agent-based transport simulation, the analysis achieves a higher degree of realism. The findings indicate that protecting one area along the coast can influence the transportation system, occasionally adversely, in regions beyond its immediate surroundings. The enhanced spatial resolution and the amalgamation of highway and transit networks within a single model unveil transportation dynamics that remained undiscovered in earlier research.

Du et al. (2017)⁵⁷ developed a model to scrutinise the operational and financial implications of water level fluctuations on the route selection decisions of shippers, the capacity of the waterway supply, and the subsequent comprehensive performance of the freight transport system linking distant communities in Canada. The results of the model offer a deeper understanding of how the multimodal transportation network might be employed and its performance (measured by delays and generalised costs) under various water level conditions, addressing uncertainties in climate and freight transport performance.

In another research, Bedoya-Maya et al. (2024)⁵⁸ examined the effects of crucial water levels on container cargo transported via the waterway along the Rhine River is conducted. Future hydrological scenarios are depicted by the count of low water days. The study demonstrates that bolstering the resilience of inland waterways to climate change is vital to prevent potential reductions in container throughput, projected to vary between 7% and 20% annual average by 2050. This research connects the short-term interactions to the long-term adaptation planning, rendering this reference a compelling one.

The following research focuses on the institutional aspect that plays a role in the adaptation decision-making of infrastructure systems, including the transport networks around the Port of Rotterdam (Mesdghi et al., 2022)⁵⁹. It introduces the Institutional Network Analysis (INA) approach, grounded in Institutional Grammar. It serves as a systematic and comprehensive instrument to (1) illustrate institutional dependencies, (2) pinpoint areas of concern in the institutional landscape such as conflicts and voids, and (3) offer quantitative insights into the centrality of actors, the embeddedness of institutional outcomes, and the interdependencies among institutions. A gap in the institutional framework is detected for financial responsibilities in areas where infrastructures intersect. The analysis uncovers a discrepancy in the application of risk assessment criteria, as entities in the Port might adhere to their individual matrices despite the existence of a collective decision-making structure.

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102568>

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rtbm.2017.02.002>

⁵⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104190>

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.10.010>

Madanat et al. (2019)⁶⁰ showed the benefits of cooperative policies for transportation network protection from sea level rise. The chosen research, despite its mono-modal scope, is noteworthy due to the application of game theory to demonstrate the advantages of collaboration in decision-making for climate adaptation. The study explores the impact of decision-maker behaviour on the likely policies for safeguarding highway infrastructure from flooding caused by rising sea levels. The model considers hydrodynamic interactions, alterations in traffic flow patterns due to flooding, and budgetary limitations on protection costs. The study proposes considering the interplay between protection measures, water levels, road closures, and increased travel time. The findings indicate that collaboration among counties generally enhances benefits (measured as a reduction in Vehicle Hours Travelled) for all involved parties.

Similar to the resilience assessment, individual modalities have been the main focus of research in adaptation planning. De Abreu et al. (2022)⁶¹ performed a systematic review of studies in the field of the road transport adaptation. The findings indicate that following the creation of the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5, 2014)⁶² by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), there has been a surge in the number of published studies on the topic, exceeding 300. This research enumerates various adaptation strategies for a range of climatological hazards, providing valuable insights for future investigations.

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2018.12.011>

⁶¹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148864>

⁶² <https://archive.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/syr/>

4. European Ports' current practices

4.1. Port infrastructure resilience and safety in maritime ports

4.1.1. Quay walls

Quay walls in ports all over Europe, are reaching the end of their original design service lifetime of approximately 50 years (Oung and Brassinga, 2015)⁶³ and many ports are working towards smart and sustainable ways to either maintain the existing quay walls or replace them with new ones. For instance, the Port of Antwerp, through an innovation called “smart quay”, has installed cameras and sensors on quays, to monitor the berthing process of ships and avoid risky overlaps (Wee, 2018)⁶⁴.

In the Port of Rotterdam, geo-monitoring and digital twin technology have been applied to a quay wall as a demonstration case, and this has shown how construction data can be used to validate numerical models of the quay wall, providing a reliable and accurate means of assessing suitability for adaptation and reuse. Furthermore, technology developed in the context of the ASHVIN programme (Duffy and Gavin, 2022⁶⁵; Gavin et al., 2023⁶⁶) has established a platform upon which future climatic trends, including increasing sea levels and temperature, can be monitored and how their influence on quay wall reliability can be assessed. Work on the ASHVIN has highlighted the challenges in fusing data from different types of construction measurements, yet once the challenges have been overcome, the benefits are numerous. Digital twin technology is gradually gaining prevalence across most sectors of the construction industry. However, the domain of geotechnical engineering is lagging behind and research into digital twin and geo-monitoring is still relatively limited (Wu et al., 2022)⁶⁷.

Work is still needed in certain areas, particularly with maximising the benefit gained from on-site construction measurements. Some research has been performed on updating numerical models based on construction measurements (e.g. den Abel, 2018⁶⁸; Li et al., 2018⁶⁹, 2021⁷⁰; Lo and Leung, 2019⁷¹) although in many cases, only synthetic data has been used and appropriately fusing different data sources has been challenging. In the CLARION project, this research gap will be explored by using data collected from the Port of Rotterdam along with publicly available case studies (Nikolinakou et al., 2011⁷²; Hsiung et al., 2016⁷³; Finno et al., 2019⁷⁴). Through this dataset, digital twin representations will be developed according to the framework established during ASHVIN and will be enhanced by using machine learning algorithms.

4.1.2. Corrosion of port infrastructure

Applying the insights about corrosion discussed in Section 3.1 to port infrastructure within the CLARION project, we can estimate the benefits of enhanced corrosion management as follows (Table 2). The four

⁶³ <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-580-7-407>

⁶⁴ <https://www.seatrade-maritime.com/europe/port-antwerp-works-towards-smart-harbour-future>

⁶⁵ <https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/01/d3-2-digital-twin-based-geo-monitoring/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/23/deliverable-4-4-risk-management/>

⁶⁷ https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1260-3_37

⁶⁸ <http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:a46ff5e1-a949-4ba7-869a-0c7db3310470>

⁶⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2018.07.026>

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2021.104051>

⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.1139/cgj-2018-0409>

⁷² [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0000518](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000518)

⁷³ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2016.07.001>

⁷⁴ [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0002010](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002010)

out of five ports in the CLARION consortium have a combined direct added value of €58.6 billion (derived from the annual reports of each of these ports – please note that the year of the latest available data might differ). The IMPACT study (NACE, 2016)²³ suggests that the corrosion cost for the maritime world is estimated at 19.9% of the added value of the ports’ economic activity, which means a loss of €11.7 billion.

Port	Direct Added Value (in € billion)	Corrosion cost (in € billion)	Corrosion sur-cost (in € billion)
		(19.9% of added value)	(15-30% of corrosion cost)
Rotterdam ⁷⁵	22	4.4	0.66-1.31
Antwerp-Bruges ⁷⁶	21	4.2	0.63-1.25
Hamburg ⁷⁷	12.4	2.5	0.37-0.75
Valencia ⁷⁸	3.2	0.64	0.096-0.192

Table 2: Calculation of estimated corrosion cost for four of the CLARION ports.

Lastly, the World Corrosion Organisation estimates that “15 to 30% of annual corrosion costs could be saved if optimum corrosion management practices were employed” (confirmed also by the IMPACT report). For the whole EU, that amounts to about €83-166 billion. Assuming ports overpay 15-30% on corrosion just like other industrial sectors this leads to an unnecessary cost of €1.8-3.5 billion.

Many companies deal with corrosion by measuring it. Currently, the global corrosion monitoring market (for production and sale of monitoring sensors) accounts for €290 million (2022) and it is estimated to grow to €820 million by 2032 with a compound annual growth rate of 11.1%. The European share is about a third thereof (€103.45 million in 2022, €275 million in 2032) (Acumen Research and Consultancy, 2023)⁷⁹. It should be noted that these data are only linked to the production of uniform corrosion, and that there are currently no sensors commercially available which are able to monitor pitting or microbial corrosion, even though these two types are responsible for 20% of corrosion damage.

Sensors are, on the other hand, not the only example of the industry’s grappling with the corrosion problem. To cite Groyzman (2016⁸⁰, 2017⁸¹):

“Many corrosion failures are caused by mismanagement in corrosion policy. The reasons of inevitability of corrosion failures and ways for their decreasing are analysed. Humans are responsible in 65-90% of corrosion cases occurring in different industries. The human factor is a key issue in corrosion management and reducing corrosion accidents. The reasons of humans’ mistakes are the lack of awareness, education, knowledge, and training, incorrect design, insufficient control and supervision, lack of motivation and incentives to reduce corrosion risk, and wrong operation.”

⁷⁵

https://www.erim.eur.nl/fileadmin/default/content/erim/research/centres/smart_port/admin/c_book_releases/havenrapport%20engelse%20versie_0.pdf

⁷⁶ https://media.portofantwerpbruges.com/m/cbd0a8ac5e5a4ab/original/BROCHURE_Cijferboekje-2023_NL.pdf

⁷⁷ <https://www.hafen-hamburg.de/en/portofhamburg/port-of-hamburg/>

⁷⁸ <https://www.valenciaport.com/en/statistics/economic-impact/>

⁷⁹ Acumen Research and Consultancy (2023) Corrosion Monitoring Market Size - Global Industry, Share, Analysis, Trends and Forecast 2023 - 2032

⁸⁰ <https://onepetro.org/NACECORR/proceedings-abstract/CORR16/All-CORR16/NACE-2016-7252/123580>

⁸¹ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-45256-2_9

Seeking effective solutions for successful corrosion management, was the subject of the recently completed Interreg project SOCORRO⁸² (2020 – 2023), which focused on the North Sea area. According to its findings, there is no general approach to determining where and when corrosion is taking place, so that preventative and remedial works can be targeted. Existing solutions tend to be generic, and there is no overall awareness of possible cost reductions. Also, any monitoring that occurs nowadays measures the effect of corrosion and not the risk: for example, in the shipping industry, sensors are merely used to determine ship plate thickness decrease as a consequence of corrosion (DNV-GL, 2016)⁸³, not to prevent corrosion. In other words, companies only react to problems which have surfaced instead of preventing them occurring in the first place. Other companies (in the offshore sector) indicate that they measure corrosion, but they lack the methodology or strategy to interpret the measurements or act upon them.

Any useful system to combat the corrosion problem, should therefore go beyond the installation of mere sensory equipment. According to Morshed (2015)⁸⁴, a corrosion report should not only contain information on the corrosion rate, but also on the chemical environment, and on the findings during cleaning and repair, as well as a risk analysis. In other words - any sensor system that is being installed, should therefore be complemented by a comprehensive, quick and easy management system to measure the local situation in a range of installations, linked to a risk assessment, based on the physicochemical conditions in which the steel resides (DuBose, 2016⁸⁵). This risk assessment should also be linked to a life-cycle cost analysis (Val & Stewart, 2003^{86, 82, 83}). Such a system should then lead to a better management of the health of industrial installations and infrastructure (e.g. Shiegg and Steiner, 2010⁸⁷; Wymore et al., 2015)⁸⁸. Morshed (2015)⁸¹ even suggests that, while a report should be composed by someone with expert knowledge, the part issued to the general management may even include a risk representation with a “traffic light” system, representing the risk with a green, yellow or red colour code, reminiscent of the analyses made by Anaf et al. (2018)⁸⁹.

Consequently, a management system should implement a full understanding of the information flow related to corrosion and corrosion conditions, from the technicians who operate the installations to the management who has to decide how to strategically act to contain the corrosion problem. This should allow for an increased general awareness that costs can be reduced even further (Schmitt, 2009)⁹⁰. Li et al. (2015)⁹¹ even defend the viewpoint that corrosion data should be freely shared to lead to a better understanding of the phenomena which every branch of the industry faces.

Within the project SOCORRO⁸², tools aiming at addressing corrosion were created, such as an AI-based algorithm to estimate corrosion rates in real time using environmental attributes, and a life cycle (cost) analysis methodology for the calculation of future corrosion-related costs from the very beginning (design phase) of a new infrastructure.

In the Port of Rotterdam, until 1999, the steel parts of the quay walls were made extra thick, and a number of quay walls were inspected for corrosion every 5 years. More recently, modern methods such as

⁸² <https://www.socorro.eu/>

⁸³ https://store.accuristech.com/standards/dnv-dnv-cg-0182?product_id=2791641

⁸⁴ <https://www.materialsperformance.com/articles/chemical-treatment/2015/12/corrosion-management-and-the-significance-of-regular-reporting>

⁸⁵ <https://www.materialsperformance.com/articles/material-selection-design/2016/07/essential-elements-of-a-successful-corrosion-management-program>

⁸⁶ [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4730\(03\)00014-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4730(03)00014-6) Get rights and content

⁸⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1002/maco.200905556>

⁸⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.07.110>

⁸⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences8080276>

⁹⁰ <http://www.corrosion.org.cn/fszy/202304/P020230501743614591484.pdf>

⁹¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/527441a>

ultrasonic measurements are used to detect corrosion by inspecting as many as one million points of horizontal and vertical locations and performing statistical analysis to the inspection results. A uniform group of measurements are placed on corrosion scales, and then corrosion rates are extrapolated within these scales and are translated to degradation. This way, a prediction regarding the remaining lifetime of the infrastructure can be made (Port of Rotterdam, 2015)⁹².

4.1.3. Shore tension for RO/RO and CON/RO terminals

During storm conditions with off land wind, special attention is being paid at the Roll on-Roll off vessel (RORO) and Container / Roll on-Roll off vessel (CONRO) terminals in the European ports. If the wind conditions are such that the moored RORO and CONRO vessels will experience high forces in their mooring lines, sometimes port authorities send out notices to the terminals and/or the captains. If the captain – which is the responsible person for the safety of the moored vessel – judges it is needed, tug assistance is called for. The tug boat (sometimes more than one) will come aside the moored vessel and push the vessel towards the quay wall. This pushing will last as long as needed, often several hours to even more than one day. This will prevent the mooring lines to be overloaded, and finally keep the moored vessel safely mooring in the port.

After some issues with large container vessels coming loose in the port of Rotterdam, the ShoreTension system was developed by the Royal Boatmen Association Eendracht (KRVE). This system consists of a strong Dyneema line connected via a hydraulic cylinder to a bollard. These ShoreTension lines are being used as additional mooring lines offering extra capacity of the moored vessel against cross winds, while the hydraulic system dampens out the motions of the moored vessel. This system is being used in pairs, preferable positioned in a symmetrical mooring configuration. In recent years quite some positive experiences have been gained with this system for moored container vessels, as well as some first experience for moored cruise vessels (Van der Burg, 2019)⁹³. After its development for the Port of Rotterdam, ShoreTension has already been applied to many ports in Europe and beyond, such as Antwerp, Bilbao, Rochelle, Bremen, Genova etc⁹⁴.

Moored RORO and CONRO vessels have – due to the stern ramp – a different non-symmetric mooring configuration and as such it is not straightforward to use the current ShoreTension system for this kind of vessels. Also the presence of the stern ramp, which act as a hinge between the moored vessel and the quay wall, gives these moored vessel another behaviour compared to container vessels. However there seems to be a potential for moored RORO and CONRO vessels, if the system is used in an intelligent way taking into account the stern ramp of those vessels. This will be studied – combining numerical study as well as in situ field tests – during the Clarion project.

4.1.4. Flood impact control

As discussed earlier in this report, the growing impact of climate change on port infrastructure and facilities may lead to a rising frequency of severe natural disasters such as SLR, increasing extreme weather, growing intensity of tropical storms and typhoons, rising wave level, and heavy rain exceeding quay wall drainage capacity. There is also the increasing risk of inland flooding in coastal lowlands due to compound events involving storm tides and heavy precipitation, particularly in the context of climate change (Bormann et al., 2024).⁹⁵ When extreme flooding occurs, ports, such as the Port of Hamburg, parts of which are

⁹² <https://aapa.files.cms-plus.com/SeminarPresentations/2015Seminars/2015FacEngineering/Voogt.pdf>

⁹³ <https://wpassets.porttechnology.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/25181924/PTI52-08.pdf>

⁹⁴ <https://www.ect.nl/sites/www.ect.nl/files/documenten/publicaties/shoretension - dynamic mooring system.pdf>

⁹⁵ <https://egusphere.copernicus.org/preprints/2024/egusphere-2024-29/egusphere-2024-29.pdf>

located in polders⁹⁶, become inaccessible. In the port of Hamburg, they are enclosed commercial areas protected from flooding by sturdy flood protection walls, dykes and terps, where the ground level is raised to a safe height. Polders are at risk due to the losses incurred by the impact of climate change, but the continuous development of flood impact protection measures can alleviate the damage potential (Yang and Ge, 2020⁹⁷; Buß et al., 2012⁹⁸; Bouwer et al., 2010⁹⁹).

Some ports, including major ones such as Rotterdam, Amsterdam and London, are already well protected against flooding, using different storm surge barriers, even against the probability of a so-called 1 in a 1000-year event (an event such intense that usually only occurs once in a thousand years). However, upgrading the existing flooding defence mechanisms is considered necessary even for those ports, given the projected rates of SLR. Other ports, such as Antwerp, Hamburg, Ghent and Gothenburg, have the physical advantage of a more protected location to begin with. It should also be taken into account, that any action towards protecting port infrastructure for inundation, would at the same time impact operations by, unavoidably, restricting the movement of ships (Christodoulou et al., 2019)¹⁰⁰.

It thus becomes apparent that robust and resilient solutions are necessary to make sure the challenges associated with flood risk management are addressed (Jonkman and Dawson, 2012)¹⁰¹. In adaptation planning, flexibility is regarded as a crucial trait for effectively responding to evolving conditions (Radhakrishnan et al., 2018)¹⁰², and adaptive planning is of utmost importance when planning for resilience (Wang et al., 2024)¹⁰³. Given the current uncertainty introduced by climate change and the continuously changing urban patterns that occur in densely-populated port cities, flexibility becomes an essential factor in flood risk management (Sörensen et al., 2016)¹⁰⁴. An example of such a port city is Hamburg, where port and flood management also includes evacuation planning, as any infrastructure stop being accessible due to floods, can have a direct impact on citizens' lives as well (Hamburg Port Authority (HPA), 2018)¹⁰⁵.

Permanent storm surge gates and flood barriers are not very common, as they involve high construction and maintenance costs and can have wider impacts on the area of application. Some examples in Europe include the Thames barrier in London, the six storm surge barriers in the Netherlands to protect the most vulnerable parts of the country, and the Venice barriers in Italy (Climate ADAPT, 2023)¹⁰⁶. While permanent flood protection systems such as dykes and protection walls are preferred in high-risk areas, in cases where space is restricted, mobile flood protection measures provide an effective alternative, and they are available with different characteristics, such as material, available protection height and safety level (Koppe and Brinkman, 2010)¹⁰⁷. The iWater project (2015-2018)¹⁰⁸ examined how storm water management can be integrated into urban planning processes at all levels, and developed common management methods, guidelines, tools and solutions for integrated storm water management, with a focus on cities of the Baltic Sea Region.

⁹⁶ Polder: a tract of low land (as in the Netherlands) reclaimed from a body of water (such as the sea) (Merriam-Webster, 2024).

⁹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2020.06.019>

⁹⁸ https://epub.sub.uni-hamburg.de/epub/volltexte/2014/33004/pdf/sturmflut_in_hamburg_1.pdf

⁹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.04.002>

¹⁰⁰ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/s41278-018-0114-z>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/4/4/785>

¹⁰² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2018.01.022>

¹⁰³ <https://doi.org/10.3390/urbansci8020051>

¹⁰⁴ <https://doi.org/10.3390/w8080332>

¹⁰⁵ https://www.hamburg-port-authority.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Broschuere_Sturmflutschutz_Ansicht.pdf

¹⁰⁶ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/storm-surge-gates-flood-barriers>

¹⁰⁷ <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3a5e/2940d175f733c2b7c16d2d786043c297ee3f.pdf>

¹⁰⁸ <https://networknature.eu/ridb/integrated-storm-water-management>

Other flood impact control measures that are met in different European ports, such as the port of Constanța¹⁰⁹, include the following:

- Installation of pumps and drainage systems from rapid water removal from the flooded areas.
- Development of detailed emergency plans, including evacuation and rescue protocols.
- Implementation of early warning systems to alert authorities and residents about the risk of flooding.
- Raising awareness of flood risks and educating the public on how to prepare and protect themselves.
- Collaborating with local and national authorities to address flood risk in a coordinated manner.
- Exchange of information and best practices with other ports facing similar flood risks.

Moreover, the use of Nature based Solutions (NbS) has also gained popularity recently as an alternative approach to flood protection (The World Bank, 2023)¹¹⁰ (for more information regarding NbS in general, see i.e. Building with nature, 2021¹¹¹; and BIO-polis, 2024¹¹², as well as section 4.1.6 of this report), and a few cities, such as Lisbon¹¹³ and the German town of Selbitz¹¹⁴ have been experimenting with the use of digital twins in flood risk management, which will be the focus of one of the CLARION pilots as well.

Overall, there is a significant shift towards resilience-based flood management strategies, as traditional flood control measures are increasingly viewed as insufficient to address current flood challenges (Wang et al., 2022)¹¹⁵. For more detailed information and an overview of the methodological spectrum used in flood risk analysis, see Diaconu et al. (2021)¹¹⁶. This review evaluates various approaches, including geospatial technologies, remote sensing, Geographic Information System (GIS), hydrological and hydraulic modelling, and statistical methods, providing valuable insights into current practices.

4.1.5. Dredged sediment reuse

Dredged sediment reuse offers numerous environmental, economic, and societal benefits, making it a valuable practice for sustainable development (Dhar and Bose, 2022)¹¹⁷. With continued innovation and adherence to regulations, dredged sediment reuse can play a significant role in environmental conservation and infrastructure development, and many ports across Europe have initiatives in this direction.

The material from the maintenance dredging works carried out in the port of Constanța is unloaded in areas where new territories will be formed: inside the future Pier IIIS, inside the "artificial island" in the river-maritime area of Constanța Port and in the Northern part of the South pier, next to the future Pier IVS. The SEDI.PORT.SIL¹¹⁸ project successfully demonstrated a pilot treatment plant to valorise almost whole

¹⁰⁹ Information received from the Port of Constanța CLARION partners.

¹¹⁰ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2023/05/22/assessing-the-benefits-and-costs-of-nature-based-solutions-for-climate-resilience-a-guideline-for-project-developers>

¹¹¹ <https://networknature.eu/ridb/building-nature>

¹¹² <https://networknature.eu/ridb/biophilic-metropolis-holistic-model-urban-planning-and-building-climate-resilience>

¹¹³ <https://www.geospatialworld.net/prime/case-study/aec/lisbons-city-scale-digital-twins-for-flood-resilience-2/>

¹¹⁴ <https://nelen-schuurmans.nl/en/case/flood-early-warning-in-a-3d-digital-twin/>

¹¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11763>

¹¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13040474>

¹¹⁷

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363769143_Dredged_Sediments_are_One_of_the_Valuable_Resources_A_Review

¹¹⁸ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE09-ENV-IT-000158/recovery-of-dredged-sediments-of-the-port-of-ravenna-and-silicon-extraction>

of dredged material samples from the Port of Ravenna in Italy, suggesting that the plant could be adapted to other European contexts as well.

Owing to its geographical location, the port of Rotterdam needs to deal with enormous amounts of sediments, mainly sands and silts, carried either by the tidal movements of North Sea or by hinterland transport from the Rhine and Meuse. The port of Rotterdam authority, through its Survey & Dredging department, is responsible for maintenance dredging in port basins. Periodic dredging must take place to keep the ports and waterways navigable.

Depending on the quality of the dredged material, which is continuously checked by the Port of Rotterdam Authority in cooperation with the Ministry of Infrastructure and Environment of the Netherlands, the dredged material is managed in two-ways. As DHV (2013)¹¹⁹ reports, if the quality of the dredged material meets the standards for beneficial use, that is no or almost no contamination, the dredged material can be relocated to the North Sea in relocation areas for the Port of Rotterdam and Rotterdam waterways, the Port of Scheveningen, the IJgeul ("IJ Trench)/Noordzeekanaal ("North Sea Canal") and the waterways towards Stellendam (Slijkgat). However, if the sediments are contaminated, these are deposited at Confined Disposal Facility (CDF) called Slufter, a 250-hectare depot constructed in 1986 as a solution for the storage of contaminated sediments (including heavy metals such as zinc and copper and organic micropollutants such as Polyhydroxy Acids (PHAs), Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), pesticides and mineral oil) from the basins of the Port of Rotterdam and surrounding fairways (Kirichek et al., 2018)¹²⁰. The activities regarding the sediment deposit at the Slufter are according to the standard ISO 14001 (ISO, 2015)¹²¹.

As stated in the Port Environmental Review System report for the port of Rotterdam (PoR, 2022)¹²², The dredging activities which are performed more than once per day include 'sediment relocation', 'sediment disposal release into water of contaminants', 'sediment storage landfills - Slufter- release of contaminants' and 'disposal waste water (dredging) (recirculation) to Water'. The range of legal and other requirements as well the control measures for each of these activities is given in details in the report.

It should be noted that the final destination of dredged material is subject to the Soil Quality Decree (Rijkswaterstaat, 2007)¹²³, which provides the Dutch interpretation in legislation for the various international treaties that regulate the management of dredged material (DHV, 2013)¹¹⁷. The Soil Quality Decree has a clear distinction between the application and the relocation of dredged material. Application of dredged materials includes beach and bank nourishment and all suppletions within the active zone of the coastal foundation, whereas relocation includes the relocation of sediment within the marine ecosystem, that is relocation of sandy dredged material within the coastal foundation, but outside the active zone.

Port of Rotterdam Authority continuously aims to improve both dredging technologies, such as the water injection dredging which involves injecting water into the sediment to create a mixture that flows away naturally (PoR, 2020)¹²⁴, as well the activities that encourage sediment reuse. The later one includes using dredged material for construction projects, habitat restoration, and land reclamation. This approach not

¹¹⁹ DHV, Royal Haskoning, Beneficial use of dredged material in North Sea – an assessment framework, Rijkswaterstaat North Sea, 2013.

¹²⁰ <https://filelist.tudelft.nl/Websections/MUDNET/Kirichek%282018%29%20Sediment%20management%20in%20the%20Port%20of%20Rotterdam.pdf>

¹²¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/60857.html>

¹²² https://www.portofrotterdam.com/sites/default/files/2021-05/port-environmental-review-system-pers-april-2020_0.pdf

¹²³ <https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/soil/legislation-and/soil-quality-decree/>

¹²⁴ <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/news-and-press-releases/port-rotterdam-authority-performing-trial-water-injection-dredging>

only reduces waste but also supports biodiversity and creates new habitats for marine life. Environmental monitoring and assessment are integral parts of these operations to ensure minimal ecological impact. One of the most significant land reclamation projects which includes dredged material, is the Maasvlakte 2 expansion (Rijks et al., 2014)¹²⁵. However, development of other port area (such as Maasvlakte 1, Europoort, Botlek Area etc.) also included extensive use of dredged materials. This land reclamation projects used millions of cubic meters of dredged sand and sediment to create new land for port facilities, contributing to the port's growth and capacity. One interesting example is the plan to transform part of the Slufter depot from dredge dump area to a useful area for solar park (PoR, 2023)¹²⁶. Another interesting example is the four-year Rijnmond Sediment Field Trial as a practical project that aims to identify different sediment-based solutions and provide insight into the possibilities for reusing dredged sand and sludge in the Rijnmond (River Rhine mouth) area (PSR, 2021)¹²⁷. There are also several initiatives where dredged material has been used for constructing infrastructure, creating building materials, and landscaping. However, as Zwakhals and Gossije (2006)¹²⁸ report, in contrast to the use of sand within projects in the harbour area, where the port can consider for each location, as an owner of the soil, the quality of the sand, for delivery of sand outside the port area national standards for building materials are required. Sand on the market can only be re-used when it meets the conditions of the right granule and chemical composition.

Another worth mentioning, recently completed, project for the port of Rotterdam, is the **SURICATES**¹²⁹ project (2017 – 2023) which developed the BROADSEAT tool which stands for "Beneficial Reuse of any Dredged Sediment Environmental Assessment Tool" (Lord and Torrance, 2021)¹³⁰. The tool uses professional judgement to compare the Beneficial Reuse Option (BRO) to the Business as Usual (BAU) case. The SURICATES large-scale effort is part of a broader initiative across Northwest Europe, intending to enhance regional resilience through innovative sediment re-use practices. The overall aim of this pilot study was to assess the efficacy of sediment reallocation to support formation of wetland areas to provide erosion protection of channel banks and to determine if such an approach could reduce the dredger sailing distance, thereby saving on CO₂ emissions. The expected outcome of the project is development of a sediment reuse sector with the increase in sediment reuse in Northwest Europe by 1.3 Mt/y after 5 years and by 2.3 Mt/y after 10 years.

Even though various applications of dredged material from port of Rotterdam can be found in literature, the research on its stabilization with the various traditional (cement or lime) or alternative (industrial by-products, geo-polymers) is so far limited and the CLARION provides a platform to find solutions for both physical – mechanical and chemical stabilization of dredged sediments. Dredged sediment reuse within the CLARION project is considered through its stabilization with the industrial by-products which would enable the potential application of the dredged sediments as the construction material. Possibilities will be analysed on the dredged material from the port of Rotterdam, as the CLARION pilot site.

¹²⁵ https://www.Utilizing_the_Full_Potential_of_Dredging_Works_Ecologically_Enriched_Extraction_Sites

¹²⁶ <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/news-and-press-releases/market-information-day-for-zon-op-de-slufter-tender>

¹²⁷ <https://www.proeftuinsediment.nl/proeftuin/>

¹²⁸ https://www.westerndredging.org/phocadownload/ConferencePresentations/2007_WODA_Florida/Session2A-DredgingProjectCaseStudies/2%20-%20Zwakhals%20-%20Dredging%20a%20New%20Harbour%20Site%20in%20the%20Port%20of%20Rotterdam.pdf

¹²⁹ <https://vb.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/suricates-sediment-uses-as-resources-in-circular-and-territorial-economies/>

¹³⁰ <https://sednet.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/2.8F-Beneficial-Reuse-Of-Any-Dredged-Sediment-Environmental-Assessment-Tool-BROADSEAT-An-open-access-tool-for-circular-economy-optioneering.pdf>

4.1.6. Nature Based Solutions for maritime ports

In the case of polluted sediments, there are several techniques based on nature, that have been applied for years to remove pollutants from soil, waters and sediments such as Phytoremediation and Bioremediation (including Biostimulation and Bioaugmentation techniques). These technologies will be explored in CLARION as a Nature based Solution (NbS) that can be useful to facilitate the reuse of polluted sediments for added value applications.

The Netherlands has adopted a relatively new approach known as 'building with nature' which makes the use of the dynamics of the natural environment and provides opportunities for natural processes. It represents a collection of coastal NbS interventions including sand engines, oyster reefs and wave-attenuating forests (De Vriend et al., 2015)¹³¹. Dunes, seagrass meadows, saltmarshes and biogenic reefs such as the mentioned oyster reefs, are able to protect coastal areas from erosion and flooding by dissipating the hydrodynamic energy through their submerged canopies or structural complexity (Hanley et al., 2014¹³²; Temmerman et al., 2013¹³³), but there are other applications and benefits associated to NbS. Some examples of working with Nature solution are detailed below.

Implementing measures to mitigate the effect of waves on port infrastructures

To combat erosion and other damage caused by waves, a number of ports have introduced nature-based solutions. Taking their inspiration from Asian ports (Taneja et al., 2020)¹³⁴, several European towns such as Agde, in France have, for example, installed mangrove breakwaters instead of traditional hard breakwaters (La Gazette des Communes, 2022)¹³⁵. These breakwaters can reduce the destructive impact of waves while generating co-benefits (development of biodiversity, spatial planning, emission capture, etc.).

Use of reef balls

Reef balls are artificial devices, i.e. not entirely based on nature, but which nevertheless play a role in improving biodiversity in coastal areas¹³⁶. They are mainly made of concrete with a pH similar to that of seawater. This helps to attract certain species and facilitate their development. The interior spaces also provide shelter for marine species. Lastly, the addition of coral plugs enables rapid growth and rescue of corals damaged by human activities (dredging) or climatic conditions (storms).

Figure 1: Reef ball (Source: Reef ball foundation, 2024)¹³⁶

Creating landscape dykes

Landscape dykes are an alternative to conventional dykes, which are sometimes not optimised from a landscape point of view and can have an impact on local biodiversity. At Noordwaard, in the Netherlands, a landscape dyke has been designed. The willow dyke is combined with the existing agile dyke to protect the area from flooding. As well as being inexpensive, it gives the landscape a new aesthetic look while

¹³¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jher.2014.06.004>

¹³² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2013.10.020>

¹³³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature12859#citeas>

¹³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.9753/icce.v36v.papers.51>

¹³⁵ <https://www.lagazettedescommunes.com/838524/erosion-cotiere-des-brise-lames-inspires-par-la-mangrove-pour-protger-la-plage/>

¹³⁶ <https://reefballfoundation.org/>

encouraging the development of local biodiversity. This protective infrastructure therefore combines safety, biodiversity and resilience to climate change (Ecoshape, 2021).¹³⁷

Figure 2: Impression of a landscape dyke

Bioremediation techniques to remove pollutants from dredged sediments

The depollution and reuse of sediments are highly relevant topics in environmental management and sustainability. Sediments accumulate in water bodies such as rivers, lakes, and reservoirs, and they can become contaminated with a variety of harmful substances, mainly hydrocarbons, which can pose significant risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health if not properly managed.

Bioremediation utilizes microorganisms that can degrade pollutants found in sediments. It is particularly effective for organic contaminants such as hydrocarbons. Bioremediation can be applied in situ (directly at the contamination site) or ex situ (after dredging the sediments). To stimulate and enhance microbial activity and therefore the biodegradation process of contaminants, microorganisms (bioaugmentation) or amendments (bio stimulation), such as air, organic substrates or other electron donors/acceptors, nutrients, and other compounds that affect and can limit treatment in their absence can be added.

Bioremediation treatments can be applied through bio piles, that are used to reduce concentrations of petroleum constituents in excavated soils and sediments using biodegradation. The effectiveness of a bio pile system depends on soil characteristics, constituent characteristics), and climatic conditions ambient. Except for the climatic conditions, most parameters can be controlled during the design and operation of the bio pile (EPA, 2017).¹³⁸ Although these technologies are well known, real trends show the need to continue improving in fundamental aspects that intervene in their correct execution and operation.

The main innovations to improve these bioremediation processes would focus on actions such as: adding materials to bio piles can activate microbial activity, improving the degradation of different carbon compounds, including heavy hydrocarbons and light fractions; Integrating composting with bio piles by adding organic bulking agents can enhance microbial activity and accelerate the breakdown of petroleum hydrocarbons in contaminated soils; Implement Real-Time Monitoring Systems, sensors and technology to continuously monitor and adjust the conditions of the bio piles, optimizing the bioremediation process. These innovations help to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of bioremediation processes in bio piles, making them more viable for treating a variety of contaminants in different environmental settings.

¹³⁷ <https://www.ecoshape.org/en/cases/wave-attenuating-willow-forest-noordwaard-nl/>

¹³⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/ust/how-evaluate-alternative-cleanup-technologies-underground-storage-tank-sites-guide-corrective>

As the CLARION pilot demonstrations regarding the effectiveness of NbS to increase the resilience of port infrastructures and deliver positive impacts will take place in the Port of Rotterdam, this sub-section summarises current practices in the port linked to NbS and environment and biodiversity management.

The Port of Rotterdam Authority has developed the “Nature Vision”, in line with the strategic “2030 Port Vision” (PoR, 2023)¹³⁹, to set out its approach to nature in the port and surrounding areas where the port has an impact, directly or indirectly. “Nature Vision” describes the areas covered and objectives established to accelerate sustainability in the port through the commitment to preserving and restoring nature and biodiversity. This includes among others, actions to:

- Keep nature in mind and connect with nature: When developing port areas, designs are created with nature in mind to prevent harming protected ecosystems and to follow nature-inclusive principles, further enhancing the existing flora and fauna.
- Provide the required ecological management to support high levels of biodiversity assessing the required mowing and removal of grass clippings based on biodiversity and port needs.
- Deliver the necessary biodiversity monitoring to control problem species, restore natural ecosystems by addressing invasive species, and track the evolution of flora and fauna for informed decision-making.

Figure 3: 2030 Port Vision. Port of Rotterdam (Source: PoR, 2023)¹³⁹

The ecological monitoring of the Port of Rotterdam is planned every year and includes both slopes and divers monitoring. The conclusions of the divers monitoring briefly describe that the surveys show that there is a great diversity of organisms in and around the water of the harbour. Studies also show that the presence of species can vary greatly at a local level and that the main factor determining species occurrence is salinity. Additionally, the type of substrate plays a significant role; steel infrastructure tends to host more species compared to slopes composed primarily of (crushed) stone.

Greening the port infrastructures and basins is important for the Port Authority of Rotterdam, which has a “Nature Opportunities Map”. Some examples of measures already applied are:

- Installation of tidal pools in the slope, 'eco modules' on poles and 'bio huts' under the walkways to the moorings (Caland Canal)
- Design of an ecological slope at the Kop van de Beer (including design of a pond)

¹³⁹ <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/sites/default/files/2023-02/port-of-rotterdam-nature-vision.pdf>

- Support to nature protection entities like ARK Nature Development and De Rijke Noordzee (St. De Noordzee) with their efforts for shellfish bank recovery in the North Sea (Native Oyster Restoration Alliance (NORA, 2020)¹⁴⁰), and moreover, because in the western part of the port, native oysters (*Ostrea edulis*) have been found, and this can be useful to facilitate further deployments of the flat oyster in other areas.

Figure 4: Native oysters in the PoR (Source: NORA, 2020)¹⁴⁰

- Quay walls construction installing Ecoblocks from Econcrete® as artificial reefs to stimulate underwater biodiversity (PoR, 2021)¹⁴¹. Deployment of the Rotterdam Reef (Reefy, 2023)¹⁴² to restore the intertidal environment for nature in the Meuse/Rhine delta. This type of breakwaters is required to protect soft shores against large ship wave and this deployment was a joint initiative where the Port Authority collaborated with the Ministry of Infrastructure, Boskalis and the City of Rotterdam.

Figure 5: Ecoblocks from Econcrete (left) and lego blocks deployed as part of the Rotterdam Reef (right)

- Creation of infrastructure to support species habitats. Existing structures made of various materials (steel, concrete, etc.) offered little grip for local species such as mussels and lacked relief. To overcome this problem, the port authorities have developed floating artificial surfaces similar to natural habitats. Made of nylon, these structures allow local species to develop their habitat without the need for costly new structures. These new devices improve habitat diversity while guaranteeing functional structures (pontoons, jetties) for the port. The Port of Rotterdam, which tested this solution, was able to observe numerous co-benefits, such as an improvement in water quality and a reduction in the concentration of fine sediments thanks to the presence of

¹⁴⁰ <https://nora-europe.eu/native-oysters-discovered-in-the-port-of-rotterdam/>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/building-port/ongoing-projects/quay-wall-construction-amaliahaven>

¹⁴² <https://reefy.nl/science/>

certain species such as mussels. Certain contaminants are also held back thanks to the presence of certain species. Finally, the complexity of the habitat allows for the development of underwater vegetation zones that encourage the development of fish (Ecoshape, 2021)¹⁴³.

Figure 6: Floating structure to promote biodiversity in the Port of Rotterdam

- Creation of tidal parks. The introduction of tidal parks allows certain port areas to be revegetated while improving flood risk management. These parks consist of planted areas along the shoreline that are filled and emptied with water according to the tides. These parks, recently tested in the port of Rotterdam, also improve biodiversity and the aesthetics of the landscape, and help to combat shoreline erosion. This solution has also been tested in the ports of the Wadden Sea (De urbanisten, 2021).¹⁴⁴

Figure 7: Impression of the Mallegatpark tidal park during low tide (top) and high tide (bottom) (Source: Van den Berg, 2018, Image from the Municipality of Rotterdam¹⁴⁵).

¹⁴³ <https://www.ecoshape.org/en/cases/habitat-opportunities-in-harbours-port-of-rotterdam-nl/>

¹⁴⁴ <https://www.urbanisten.nl/work/river-as-tidal-park-rotterdam>

¹⁴⁵ www.ecoshape.org/en/cases/building-with-nature-in-delta-cities-dordrecht-and-rotterdam-nl/planning-and-design-phase/

On the other hand, considering that the Port of Rotterdam is one of the most important ports in the world and that the shipping industry is growing globally, with vessels increasing in size to meet the demand, higher drafts are necessary to keep the port accessible. As a result, the Port of Rotterdam requires intensive maintenance dredging that yields 12–15 million m³ of dredged material annually (Kirichek et al., 2018)¹⁴⁶.

The quality of the sediment in the port basins has been monitored via an annual monitoring campaign for several decades. The destination of dredged material is subject to the Soil Quality Decree and only salty dredged material that meets the standards may be relocated to sea in the specific relocation areas defined. The rest is stored in confined disposal facility such as the Slufter on the Maasvlakte (Boskalis, 2024)¹⁴⁷.

Figure 8: Slufter: confined disposal facility¹⁴⁷

Since the construction of the disposal facility and the implementation of measures taken to address contamination at the source in the Rhine basin, the water quality in the port basins and fairways improved significantly. As a result, the volume of contaminated dredged material drastically dropped, prolonging the operational lifespan of the Slufter disposal site until 2050¹⁴⁶. Apart from traditional sediments management, the Port of Rotterdam (PoR) has experience on the use of NbS to remove pollutants from dredged materials, in particular using bioremediation techniques to remove polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) from harbour sludges.

In many ports, such as the Port of Rotterdam, the existing structures made of various materials (steel, concrete, etc.) offered little grip for local species such as mussels and lacked relief. To overcome this problem, the port authorities have developed floating artificial surfaces similar to natural habitats. Made of nylon, these structures allow local species to develop their habitat without the need for costly new structures. These new devices improve habitat diversity while guaranteeing functional structures (pontoons, jetties) for the port.

The Port of Rotterdam, which tested this solution, was able to observe numerous co-benefits such as an improvement in water quality and a reduction in the concentration of fine sediments. Certain contaminants are also held back thanks to the presence of certain species. Finally, the complexity of the habitat allows for the development of underwater vegetation zones that encourage the development of fish (Ecoshape, 2021)¹⁴³.

¹⁴⁶ <https://pure.tudelft.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/99008340/Kirichek2018SedimentmanagementinthePortofRotterdam.pdf>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.boskalisbeheerslufteer.nl/>

The digital monitoring of nature-based solutions is addressed in some scientific research literature. Tsekeri et al. (2022)¹⁴⁸ indicate that several digital tools can be used to monitor the performance of nature-based solutions, such as IoT tools, sensors and databases for storing and analysing information gathered in the field. The use of sensors, coupled with other technologies, appears to be an effective way of carrying out this digital monitoring. Several types of sensors can be used to collect data. Some of them can be used to measure the temperature or humidity in the vicinity of certain solutions, and can therefore directly inform the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) once these have been defined. By coupling these sensors with digital platforms and cross-referencing the data using advanced technologies (IoT), it seems possible to carry out digital monitoring of nature-based solutions and their impacts.

Figure 9: Link between the NbS and the digital monitoring (Source: Ecoshape, 2021¹⁴³).

4.2. Transport resilience and safety in maritime ports

4.2.1. Resilience of connected inland waterways, roads and railways infrastructure

As discussed in Section 3.2, the transportation system is subject to changing climatic conditions. The scale and frequency of disruptions due to climate change are expected to increase in the future. The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (in Dutch: Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut - KNMI) calculated four different future climate scenarios, and all of them predict rising sea levels and temperatures, drier summers, and more wet winters (KNMI, 2023)¹⁴⁹. Such climatic changes significantly impact transport networks and their functionality. For instance, drought can reduce the capacity to transport cargo via inland waterways, emphasizing the importance of switching to alternative modes such as rail or road during such events. Investigating potential impacts of climate change and adaptation strategies becomes necessary, which includes the sensitivity to climate threats per asset and the consequences at the system level. Such analyses determine, among other things, damage, loss (for the user/carrier), critical network elements, and a set of high-level adaptation strategies.

The transportation sector is presently confronting concurrent challenges due to geopolitical changes, climate change impacts, and issues related to energy security. The intensity of these challenges is influenced by the specific traits of the networks that are impacted. Predicting future disruptions is fraught with uncertainty. Despite advancements in risk assessment, only few governments utilize available tools

¹⁴⁸ https://surreal.tuc.gr/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/On_the_integration_of_nature-based_solutions_with_digital_innovation_for_health_and_wellbeing_in_cities.pdf

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.knmi.nl/research/publications/knmi-23-klimaatscenario-s-voor-nederland>

to identify potential hazards. These tools include horizon scanning, vulnerability analysis of network attributes, digital twins, and advanced transport modelling (ITF, 2024)¹⁵⁰.

Europe's critical infrastructure (CI) is under threat of collapse due to natural hazards and swift climate change, potentially resulting in significant physical and economic damage. Current methods for analysing climate risk are not specifically designed for the intricacies of CI: they fail to adequately consider system interdependencies and still contain crucial data voids (MIRACA consortium, 2021)¹⁵¹.

Public authorities are in urgent need of instruments to identify areas at risk and formulate cost-effective adaptation strategies to bolster Critical Infrastructure (CI) resilience. The objective of the on-going Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment for Climate Adaptation (MIRACA) project (2023-2027) is to instigate and facilitate the execution of adaptation measures for CI across Europe. The MIRACA consortium (2021)¹⁵¹ aims at creating an evidence-based decision-support toolkit, comprising a guide on the technical and economic evaluation of adaptation strategies, a technical workbench, and an online interactive viewer. These will be grounded in a multi-hazard climate risk assessment framework that utilises innovative methods of data collection, which will bridge critical gaps in understanding the vulnerability and costs of critical infrastructure. Another interesting case is the open-source Digital Twin (DT) of the Dutch waterways (Deltares, 2024)¹⁵². This DT combines data on infrastructure, hydrodynamics, and vessel behaviour to model the potential effects of climate change impacts and adaptation strategies, both infrastructural and logistical, on the performance of inland waterways. It utilises agent-based simulation tools, such as OpenCLSim and OpenTNSim, developed by TU Delft.

Critical infrastructure that will influence both the distribution of water and the Inland Water Transport (IWT) performance, such as locks, bridges, and terminals, are sourced from European River Information System -EuRIS contains all information needed for skippers, vessel owners or logistic operators on the main European waterways. The DT also incorporates varying inputs and parameters, including estimates of the energy and emission footprints of the installed engine. This tool enables the simulation of the intricate interactions of ships with water depths, flow velocities, and hydraulic structures in a more realistic manner than the MHRM. This is particularly relevant when considering the complexities of managing transport infrastructure exposed to multiple hazards, contributing to building resilience.

According to a research study by the Netherlands Institute for Transport Policy Analysis (KiM) (Tillema et al., 2021)¹⁵³, important knowledge gaps concern the impact of climate change on infrastructure, its use, and transport patterns, as well as questions about spatial planning and behavioural adjustments. Early warning systems and communication add value in dealing with the impact of climate change on infrastructure, while policy discussions focus on strategic considerations such as whether to make entire corridors climate-proof and differentiating measures according to network importance.

Based on research performed by Sweco (2022)¹⁵⁴, weather extremes lead to increasing damages, and reducing the impact of these challenges requires a better understanding of cascading effects and uncertainties in the to-be-propagated impacts. Identifying and addressing these knowledge gaps is essential to enhance the resilience of the transport system and for future climate-related disruptions. The effects of climate change on hinterland transport are frequently examined for individual, or single-modal,

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/transport-system-resilience.pdf>

¹⁵¹ <https://miraca-project.eu/>

¹⁵² <https://cms.deltares.nl/assets/common/downloads/Deltares-Digital-Twin-Position-Paper.pdf>

¹⁵³ <https://www.kimnet.nl/publicaties/rapporten/2021/07/01/klimaatverandering-en-het-mobiliteitssysteem>

¹⁵⁴ Sweco. (2022). Beleidsprioriteiten Focuspunt Klimaatadaptatie RWS.

transport networks. An example is the study conducted by Deltares (van Marle, de Groen, et al., 2024)¹⁵⁵, which explored the sensitivity and resilience of the Dutch road, railway, and inland waterway network to climate change. Open-source instruments, like RA2CE (Resilience Assessment and Action perspective for Critical infrastructure), have been devised to carry out such resilience assessments, even at the scale of the entire European road network. RA2CE serves as a valuable tool for stakeholders in infrastructure, facilitating the execution of resilience assessments and the identification of appropriate adaptation strategies. It accomplishes this by creating detailed resilience maps for events induced by climate change, thereby highlighting feasible adaptation alternatives. This comprehensive approach ensures that all potential impacts are considered, and the most effective strategies are implemented. These tools offer a comprehensive perspective on the potential impacts and necessary actions to enhance the resilience of critical infrastructure (Deltares, 2021)¹⁵⁶.

Bles et al. (2023)¹⁵⁷ illustrate the application of resilience quantification and evaluation in formulating an action plan for climate adaptation pertaining to a road network, with a specific focus on the Netherlands' highway system. The analysis is a two-pronged process. Initially, a stress-test is conducted using the RA2CE modelling framework to estimate the annual expected damages and losses under current and future scenarios, considering potential impacts of climate change across ten distinct climate hazards. Following this, a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and resilience evaluation are employed to pinpoint potential interventions and their optimal locations.

According to KBN¹⁵⁸ (2023) and regarding the Dutch waterway transport, it is essential to invest in better depth measurements, forecasting tools, and the flexibilization of freight flows. Developing a reliable multi-week forecast of water levels and creating a 'digital twin' environment for waterways offers promising possibilities. A systematic approach and close collaboration among all involved parties are crucial to increase the resilience of the transport system and prepare the Netherlands for future challenges.

Recent research by TNO focused on the challenges of Dutch railway transport in maintaining its transport share under disruptions and due to future technological changes in other modalities (Van Buerenplein et al., 2023)¹⁵⁹. This study concluded that paradigm-shifting innovations must be implemented in the rail system to improve its competitive position. Such solutions include automated train operations, real-time traffic management, deployment of short and mixed freight trains, and non-craneable trailer trains. Therefore, and from a resilience perspective, interventions are needed for the rapid and flexible creation of transport capacity during disruptions, for instance, during periods of low water rail transport can attract transport share from inland waterway networks.

Moreover, developing and deploying a platform to facilitate additional capacity among stakeholders, constructing different railway routes between certain key locations, and developing an escalation protocol to systematically take measures can improve the effectiveness of the response during and just before disruptions. According to Van Meijeren & Harmsen (2020)¹⁶⁰, further development and exploration of the technical and organizational feasibility of implementing such measures are needed. This study identified sets of measures to increase the capacity of the railway network to respond to expected modal shifts during periods of low water. The key measures include maximizing the use of existing wagon sets, increasing

¹⁵⁵ van Marle, M., de Groen, F., van Ginkel, K., Bles, T., Soriano Perez C., & Woning, M. (2024). Resilience Assessment and Adaptation for Critical Infrastructure – Modelling Resilient Infrastructure Systems. Transport Research Arena (TRA).

¹⁵⁶ <https://www.kimnet.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2021/07/01/bijlage-rapport-klimaatverandering-en-het-mobiliteitssysteem>

¹⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2023.11.508>

¹⁵⁸ Koninklijke Binnenvaart Nederland (KBN). (2023). Laagwatervisie voor de binnenvaart in Nederland en op de Rijn.

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.dinalog.nl/project/a-paradigm-shift-in-rail-freight-transport/>

¹⁶⁰ Van Meijeren, J., & Harmsen, J. (2020). RAIL AS CONTINGENCY MODE FOR BARGE IN SITUATIONS WITH LOW WATER LEVELS ON THE RHINE FINAL REPORT, OCTOBER 2020

frequency with existing equipment, adding extra trains with additional equipment, or using longer trains on a temporary basis. While organizing and implementing such measures requires time and resources, these resources are worth investing given the high damages (€2.7 billion in 2018 in the Netherlands and Germany combined). However, there is a need to further identify the quantitative impact of such measures on freight transport.

In research conducted by Melkonyan et al. (2024)¹⁶¹, a qualitative method is adopted to scrutinise mitigation and adaptation strategies within the logistics sector. It delves into the obstacles transportation firms encounter in formulating climate-neutral business models and adjusting to the repercussions of climate change. Expert interviews form the crux of the methodology. The findings reveal that logistics firms require enhanced preparedness for the impacts of climate change and concurrently, they inadequately tackle climate change mitigation, rendering the sector increasingly susceptible to future climate extremes.

Multi-modal adaptation planning examples in practice are scarce. Two studies focusing on the road network are presented below:

Rijkswaterstaat (Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management of the Netherlands) is working towards a climate-resilient main road network by 2050, with strategies to combat “ponding due to extreme rainfall” (de Bel et al., 2021)¹⁶². The research suggests that intensified maintenance is the most efficient strategy. Economically viable measures include monitoring and adjusting verge height, cleaning gullies and wells more frequently, and installing additional gullies where needed. These strategies should be discussed with asset managers for potential inclusion in road management and maintenance. While some measures may not be economically effective, they may still be considered for their broader benefits, such as biodiversity, safety, sustainability, or CO₂ reduction, which are not included in the economic analysis. This research has considered the sensitivity of the main road network to ponding. Subsequently, measures have been identified to counteract ponding and the effectiveness of these measures has been estimated. Finally, with a trade-off of costs and benefits, promising measures have been identified to make the main road network more climate-resilient. The benefits are defined as a decrease in the negative consequences of ponding in terms of recovery and congestion costs.

The study performed by van Marle, de Paor, et al. (2024)¹⁶³ aids in the execution of climate change adaptation strategies within the processes of national road authorities. It offers tangible guidance on the practical implications of adaptation implementation. This is achieved through case studies and practical examples, illustrating the application of methodologies outlined in previous deliverables within the ICARUS project. The practical examples commence when the results of the resilience assessment reveal that the network's performance does not meet the stipulated requirements, and outlines the necessary steps to identify the appropriate adaptation. Initially, the implementation of 10 critical adaptation measures is illustrated with detailed descriptions concerning (i) instructions for their execution, (ii) methods for valuing costs, benefits, and co-benefits, and (iii) best practices.

4.2.2. Extreme weather forecasting

Extreme weather events put port infrastructure at major risk and can disrupt the operations and have a negative impact on safety. According to a UNCTAD survey (2017)¹⁶⁴ addressed to port authorities located in 29 different countries all over the world, more than 70% of them are being affected by extreme weather

¹⁶¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2024.101102>

¹⁶² de Bel, M., van Marle, M., & Kwant, M. (2021). Handelingsperspectief Rijkswaterstaat voor plasmvorming op het hoofdwegennet.

¹⁶³ van Marle, M., de Paor, C., Toft Andersen, T., Bülow Gregersen, I., Bles, T., Lamb, M., de Bel, M., Garcia Sanchez, D., & Connolly, L. (2024). Demonstration report showing how principle adaptation measures can be evaluated.

¹⁶⁴ https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ser-rp-2017d18_en.pdf

events that cause delays, disruptions in operations and damages in infrastructure. Extreme weather can include extreme high/low temperature, extreme rainfall, extreme wind (Li et al., 2023)¹⁶⁵, high waves, storms, lightning and intense fog (buluttan, 2024¹⁶⁶), hurricanes and floods (UNCTAD, 2022)¹⁶⁷. Being able to forecast these events as effectively as possible is a very important element in building a successful port resilience strategy. The use of advanced extreme weather forecasting tools allows ports to anticipate and thus be better prepared for adverse weather conditions; this way, they can reduce response time, prevent infrastructure damage and ensure the safety of personnel and cargo.

Ports around Europe are using different approaches to forecasting, with some of them employing more advanced tools such as Internet of Things' sensors and augmented intelligence, combined with hydro and meteo data for instance in the Port of Rotterdam¹⁶⁸. Applying Digital Twin technology to port environments to help in extreme weather forecasting, which is the focus of one of the CLARION pilots, is a new and emerging field of DT application, with the project SAFARI Ports¹⁶⁹ (2024 – 2027) also aiming at deploying a DT to enhance operational resilience in the ports of Seville, Dunkirk and Lisbon.

The role of DTs for climate risk reduction in general, as well as the use of Artificial Intelligence(AI) to model climate change^{170,171,172}, have recently gathered increasing interest as a research topic. For instance, Johannsen, et al., (2023)¹⁷³, focusing on urban resilience, present a comprehensive approach to tackling climate change through the creation of a DT network for urban adaptation. By providing a virtual representation of city infrastructures and systems and integrating various data sources and modelling techniques, it highlights the role of environmental informatics in developing and implementing innovative solutions for planning towards resilience. While the use of DT concepts to enhance the climate resilience of cities is gaining popularity in the research community, its effectiveness should be tested in real world applications to analyse the results and showcase potential benefits to policy makers, stakeholders and citizens, before wide implementation would be possible (Riaz et al., 2023)¹⁷⁴.

4.2.3. Cadastral measurements and inland water level forecasting

The European inland waterways comprise a network of more than 40,000 km and includes canals, rivers and lakes and it is particularly dense in North-western Europe. Most industrial areas in Central Europe, as well as all major seaports can be reached via inland waterway transport (Imprex, 2016)¹⁷⁴. For the ports which are connected to the hinterland through inland waterways, monitoring them is of critical importance, due to their exposure in extreme weather events, such as droughts, storms, and flash floods. Inland water level and its dynamics are key components of the global water cycle and land surface hydrology and has a strong impact on climate variability.

As water levels rise, ports face risks of flooding, erosion, and damage of critical facilities. By continuously monitoring inland water levels, port authorities can proactively assess potential hazards and implement preventive measures. Hydro-meteorological and hydrological forecasting, being part of River Information

¹⁶⁵ <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1104045>

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.buluttan.com/blog/severe-weather/effects-of-extreme-weather-events-on-port-operations>

¹⁶⁷ <https://resilientmaritimelogistics.unctad.org/guidebook/12-extreme-weather-events>

¹⁶⁸ <https://www.ibm.com/blogs/think/2018/01/smart-port-rotterdam/>

¹⁶⁹ https://www.linkedin.com/company/safariports?trk=public_post-text

¹⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0083>

¹⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23052659>

¹⁷² <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14223619>

¹⁷³ https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-18311-9_10

¹⁷⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311455497_IMPREG_D91_Vulnerability_of_Inland_Waterway_Transport_and_Waterway_Management_on_Hydro-meteorological_Extremes/figures?lo=1

Services¹⁷⁵ (RIS), are considered a robust tool in improving efficiency and facilitating the strategic management of inland waterways (Imprex, 2016)¹⁷⁴.

Historically, observations for inland water surface heights monitoring, and therefore understanding of global hydrological cycle, relies on in-situ gauge measurements. The gauge levels are defined by location-specific characteristic, which should be considered in the assessment process of the impact of projected discharges (EU IWT Platform, 2021)¹⁷⁶. Sensors are sometimes used to retrieve water level heights, enabling efficient monitoring at very high temporal resolutions. Recent research activities, such as the ReNEW project¹⁷⁷, aim to increase uptake of such digital innovations in order to formulate dataspaces and DTs for green and resilient inland waterways.

However, existing in-situ networks are still sparse to support large scale applications, and also the availability of ground-based gauge observations has been steadily decreasing during the last decades, particularly in areas with difficult access. In this context, space-based remote sensing has emerged as a cost-effective technique that provides up-to-date measurements from various sensors with global coverage and homogeneous accuracy. The initiation of Open-Loop Tracking Command (OLTC), and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) mode, have boosted the use of altimetry missions for inland water level monitoring (for more information see Kossieris et al., 2024¹⁷⁸).

On-going initiatives in Europe investigate further the role of novel digital tools; for instance, the project PLOT0¹⁷⁹ (2022-2026), focuses on the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of inland water ways against climate change and other extremes, with an application in the Danube area (Liparas and Vamvatsikos, 2023)¹⁸⁰.

4.2.4. EMS for extreme weather events

European ports are actively improving their Emergency Management Systems (EMS) with a sophisticated health monitoring and emergency control system, influenced by advanced methodologies developed through various previous and ongoing EU projects such as PRECINCT, SAFARI, FORESEE, RESIST, MOWE-IT, EWENT, ECCONET, RESOLUTE, CHARIOT, CIPROTECTION, ZONeSEC and ANYWHERE. The EMS attempts to improve resilience in essential transportation infrastructure networks by tackling complex links and cyber-physical interdependencies. The EMS can utilize insights into how disruptions in one sector can cascade to other systems, which is critical for managing severe events like storms, flash floods, heatwaves, and droughts.

Using a combined approach of automation theory and graph theory is a key component of the EMS and a state-of-the-art method as well. This method uses probabilistic automaton models to represent operational changes within individual Critical Infrastructures (CIs) as inner models, and graph models to explain functional interdependencies among CIs in an outer model. This methodology uses dependencies in the outer model to depict cascading effects and effectively characterises probabilistic state changes within CIs produced by incidents. The impacts of these state changes on interconnected CIs are further simulated using simulation methods based on Markov chain models, which offer statistical insights into incident

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.eurisportal.eu/RIS?KL=en>

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/forecasting-the-impacts-of-climate-change-on-inland-waterways/>

¹⁷⁷ <https://renew-waterways.eu/>

¹⁷⁸ <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16071181>

¹⁷⁹ <https://ploto-project.eu/>

¹⁸⁰ https://www.inlandwaterwaytransport.eu/wp-content/uploads/PLOT0-project_Liparas_Inland-Navigation-Week.pdf

severity, propagation patterns, and critical nodes. These insights improve the overall resilience of port infrastructures by helping operators predict and mitigate cascade effects more successfully.

Moreover, the EMS's framework can incorporate sophisticated modelling and simulation capabilities, enabling dynamic scenario analysis and crisis response strategy optimisation. The solution improves the security, integrity, and control of smart sensors and infrastructure components by utilising cognitive architectures and IoT platforms. The EMS may benefit from continuous threat assessment provided by real-time data from pilots and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This would enable adaptive response planning and guarantee operational continuity during important events.

While extreme weather (Stamos et al., 2015)¹⁸¹ and natural disasters impact ports globally, they pose particularly severe challenges for terminals in developing EU countries. Those countries, lacking in infrastructure and with their economies heavily reliant on maritime imports, are heavily affected by these disruptions. However, efforts are underway globally to strengthen port resilience. Additionally, global guidelines and case studies from associations like the International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH) inform resilience strategies, aiding ports in preparing for and mitigating future crises.

Based on the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (Lee and Romero, 2023)¹⁸², supply chain management optimisation and flexible infrastructure development are some of the proactive steps that need to be taken in response to the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events. By taking such actions, European ports can lower risks, keep operations running, and set the base for a resilient and sustainable maritime transport infrastructure (Verschuur et al., 2020)¹⁸³.

4.3. Best practices outside the EU

While European ports are taking decisive steps towards becoming green and resilient, as discussed in the previous sections of this report, it is worth looking at how different ports worldwide are building their defence mechanisms to address the impact of climate change and at lessons learnt from best practices in the field of port resilience.

The importance of effectively involving stakeholders in all stages of planning for resilience, by increasing collaboration and information sharing, is highlighted in the case of the Port of New York, USA. The port was hit by superstorm Sandy in 2012, which caused flooding in the majority of the port area, the death of 280 people in the port community, severe damages in infrastructure and major disruptions in port operations, which had to cease for eight days. The port is working since then to enhance the effective joint pre-event preparation, by promoting coordination and clear role definitions between port stakeholders, building trust and strengthening institutional relationships (UNCTAD, 2024)¹⁸⁴.

The Port of Long Beach, in California, prepared in 2016 a Climate Adaptation and Coastal Resiliency Plan to identify vulnerabilities and define risks and adaptation strategies towards the climate hazards of extreme heat, sea level rise, and storm surge. The process, which involved port employees through the means of workshops, concluded in the selection and implementation of five adaptation strategies, some of which are characterized as financially low-impact, but high-value, such as actively including climate change impacts into port policies, plans, and guidelines (Kim and Ross, 2019)¹⁸⁵. The neighbouring Port

¹⁸¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2014.11.002>

¹⁸² https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/syr/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_SYR_SPM.pdf

¹⁸³ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102393>

¹⁸⁴ <https://resilientmaritimelogistics.unctad.org/guidebook/case-study-12-port-new-york-united-states>

¹⁸⁵ https://www.resilienceshift.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/RP-Ports_Final_Pages.pdf

of Los Angeles (together with the Port of Long Beach they form the San Pedro Bay Port Complex, handling 40% of the container volume entering the US), has the largest number of shore powering facilities comparing to any other port of the world; the term refers to electrical hookups, with the use of which berthed ships are able to turn off their engine reducing drastically emissions (Bertrand and Williams, 2022)¹⁸⁶. The process of berthing has been improved also in the Port of Singapore, with the help of OptEVoyage, a digital tool that integrates real time information 24/7, facilitating ship-to-port data exchange and allowing vessels to arrive in precisely accurate berth times, leading in major GHG emission reduction (WPSP, 2022)¹⁸⁷.

OptEVoyage is a digital solution that synchronises transparent real-time activities and 24/7 ship-to-port data exchange between carrier and port operator to enable Just-In-Time vessel arrivals for berth.

Around the world, several coastal areas have already experimented with digital monitoring techniques to collect data that can be used to track the performance of nature-based solutions. In Thailand, the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMU) has developed, on two pilot sites (the Yom and Sakaekrang river basins in northern and western Thailand), the implementation of climate change mitigation measures using nature-based solutions. A monitoring and evaluation methodology based on a digital tool has also been developed to assess the impacts and benefits of nature-based solutions on the climate resilience of the area concerned¹⁸⁸ (Thai-German Climate Programme, 2020). This solution has also been used by the Port of Miami, which has restored more than 15 hectares of mangroves. Other US ports, such as the Port of San Diego, have been able to test the co-benefits of this solution by also finding a use for these landscaping solutions for flood management. The Port of Portland is using rain gardens and vegetated swales as green infrastructure for managing stormwater and the Port of Seattle employs oyster shells in stormwater catchment basins so as copper can be removed by the increase in the amount of dissolved calcium and magnesium in the water (Bertrand and Williams, 2022)¹⁸⁶.

In terms of dredged sediment reuse, the Maryland Port Administration is using dredged material from the Port of Baltimore to restore the previously eroded Poplar Island in the Chesapeake Bay (Bertrand and Williams, 2022)¹⁸⁶. The Port of Brisbane, in Australia is reusing dredged material to create new port land (WPSP, 2019)¹⁸⁹, and so does Port of Auckland, in New Zealand (CEDA, 2024)¹⁹⁰. Tuas port, an ongoing mega-project in Singapore, being developed in four phases, when fully operational has the ambition to become the world's single largest container port with a handling capacity of up to 65 million Twenty-foot Equivalent Units (TEUs) annually. In order to address SLR, Tuas port will have an operational platform of 5m above mean sea level and more than half of the total fill materials for the two first phases of the project will be re-used dredged material (WPSP, 2019)¹⁹¹.

In Latin America, the Port Industrial Complex of Bahía Blanca, Villarino, Puerto Belgrano and Coronel Rosales in Argentina has established a Port 2040 sustainable strategy according to the philosophy of "Working with Nature" (PIANC – The World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure) (Port Authority of Bahia Bianca, 2018)¹⁹². The results of an international working group on port climate resilience with a of focus on the Port of Açú, Brazil, highlight the necessity of taking local circumstances into account, as local effects of climate change can differentiate from global average, and therefore tailored-made strategies have the potential be more effective (WPSP, 2022)¹⁹³.

¹⁸⁶ <https://www.eesi.org/papers/view/issue-brief-climate-change-mitigation-and-adaptation-at-u.s-ports-2022>

¹⁸⁷ <https://sustainableworldports.org/project/psa-singapore-optevoyage/>

¹⁸⁸ https://www.thai-german-cooperation.info/en_US/thai-german-climate-programme-water/

¹⁸⁹ <https://sustainableworldports.org/project/port-of-brisbane-beneficial-reuse-of-dredge-material/>

¹⁹⁰ <https://dredging.org/resources/ceda-publications-online/beneficial-use-of-sediments-case-studies/13/>

¹⁹¹ <https://sustainableworldports.org/project/maritime-and-port-authority-of-singapore-singapores-next-generation-port/>

¹⁹² https://puertobahia blanca.com/vision_portuaria_2040/files/downloads/Vision_BB_2040-EN.pdf

¹⁹³ <https://sustainableworldports.org/project/port-of-acu-climate-resilience/>

5. Existing Initiatives & Collaborative Communities

5.1. International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH)

IAPH¹⁹⁴ is a non-governmental organization (NGO) headquartered in Tokyo, Japan. In November 1955, some 100 world port leaders gathered in Los Angeles to announce the creation of IAPH. Over the past six decades, IAPH has developed into a global alliance of ports, representing today some 177 ports and 147 port-related businesses in 84 countries. The member ports together handle well over 60% of the world's sea-borne trade and over 60% of the world container traffic. IAPH aims to be the global trade association of choice for port authorities and operators, representing their interests at regulatory level at the International Maritime Organization, the World Customs Organization, the International Standards Organization and other global alliances such as the Global Maritime Forum and the World Economic Forum.

IAPH has consultative status and works on behalf of ports with additional United Nations bodies such as the UNCTAD (UN Conference on Trade and Development), UNEP (UN Environment Program) and the UN Global Compact. It has established the World Ports Sustainability Program in order to assist ports in applying the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals in practice. The program is aimed at enhancing and coordinating future sustainability efforts of ports worldwide and fostering international cooperation with partners in the supply chain. The program wants to empower port community actors worldwide to engage with business, governmental and societal stakeholders in creating sustainable added value for the local communities and wider regions in which their ports are embedded.

5.2. European Sea Ports Organisation (ESPO)

In 1974, the European Commission set up a Port Working Group, consisting of port authority representatives from Europe's major ports. Early 1993, the European Sea Ports Organisation was born out of this working group, as an independent lobby for seaport interests. Founding Chairman was the late Ferdinand Suykens, former director-general of the Port of Antwerp. During its initial years of existence, the organisation established itself in Brussels, focusing on a variety of policy and technical issues. ESPO¹⁹⁵ represents the common interests and promotes the common views and values of its members to the European institutions and its policy makers. Significant initiatives were the publication of the first Environmental Code of Practice in 1994 and the establishment of EcoPorts a few years later. The founding principle of EcoPorts is to create a level playing field on environment through cooperation and sharing of knowledge between ports. To this purpose two tools have been developed within EcoPorts; the Self Diagnosis Method (SDM) and the Port Environmental Review System (PERS). (SDM) is a concise checklist against which port managers can self-assess the environmental management program of the port in relation to the performance of both the sector and international standards. PERS, developed by ports, incorporates the main general requirements of recognised environmental management standards (e.g. ISO 14001), taking into account the specificities of ports.

¹⁹⁴ <https://www.iaphworldports.org/>

¹⁹⁵ <https://www.espo.be/>

5.3. International Port Community Systems Association (IPCSA)

IPCSA¹⁹⁶ members are Sea and Air Port Authorities, Port Community System Operators for both sea and air, and Single Window Operators.

The electronic exchange platforms provided by IPCSA's members enable the electronic flow of Business to Business, Business to Government and Government to Government information. These platforms underpin smooth, efficient transport and logistics operations at hundreds of sea ports, airports and inland ports, linking the flow of operational and administrative/regulatory processes and removing paper from the supply chain. IPCSA focuses on supporting and facilitating systems and innovations for its members and their users, and promoting the use of international data standards in sea and air ports, at border crossings and via Single Window systems around the world.

5.4. Green Ports Forum

The Green Ports Forum¹⁹⁷ is a global initiative launched by C40, in collaboration with the City of Los Angeles and the Port of Los Angeles, to advance maritime decarbonization. It connects 20 of the world's leading port cities, providing a platform for these ports to exchange knowledge and collaborate on achieving climate goals in an economically sustainable way. The forum focuses on coordinated actions to reduce emissions and tackle the climate crisis, aiming to set targets for decarbonizing global supply chains related to ports in a just and equitable manner.

5.5. WATERBORNE

WATERBORNE¹⁹⁸ has been set up as an industry-oriented Technology Platform to establish a continuous dialogue between all waterborne stakeholders, such as classification societies, shipbuilders, shipowners, maritime equipment manufacturers, infrastructure and service providers, universities, or research institutes, and with the EU Institutions, including Member States.

The strategic objectives of the WATERBORNE TP are:

- Establish a continuous dialogue between all stakeholders in the waterborne transport sector and in other waterborne-related sectors on R&D;
- Contribute to the widest possible consensus regarding R&D and to focusing of efforts and resources.
- Develop a common medium- and long-term R&D Vision and a Strategic Research Agenda (SRA);
- Contribute to the appropriate mobilization and allocation of the necessary financial resources (private/regional/national/EU sources);
- Contribute to the social expectations regarding clean, competitive, and safe waterborne transport as well as regarding other waterborne-related activities, including education and training.

¹⁹⁶ <https://ipcsa.international/>

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.c40.org/what-we-do/scaling-up-climate-action/ports-and-shipping/green-ports-forum/>

¹⁹⁸ <https://www.waterborne.eu/>

5.6. chainPORT

Initiated by Hamburg Port Authority and the Port of Los Angeles, chainPORT¹⁹⁹ is a cross-national partnership among the world's leading ports. By sharing innovations or strategic topics, the members learn from each other and share their best practices. For example, an extensive debate on the impact of the digital revolution on ports is ongoing. Another central theme of the exchange is the efficient use of existing port infrastructure and the related optimization of investment decisions.

5.7. Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE)

ALICE²⁰⁰ is the Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe²⁰¹ a non-for-profit industry led association based in Brussels with 170+ members reaching the full stakeholders' groups within freight transport, logistics and supply chain including ports, terminals, hinterland ports and transport operators. ALICE is the Alliance of European leading companies and experts in implementing logistics and supply chain innovation.

ALICE vision is to achieve an affordable transition towards zero emissions logistics contributing to climate change objectives. To that end, logistics, from global to urban, need to evolve. Assets and resources, including transportation means, need to be better utilized. By creating seamlessly interconnected logistics networks through the Physical Internet (PI) the conditions for affordability of zero emissions solutions through sharing will be created, contributing to further agility and resilience of supply chains. One of the key elements in the Physical Internet roadmap is the key role of logistics nodes to achieve efficient and resilient supply chains.

ALICE supports, assists, and advises the European Commission²⁰² in the definition and implementation of the EU Program for research: Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe in Logistics. ALICE can direct Research and Innovation needs of ports and ports stakeholders in the area of freight transport and logistics into the Horizon Europe programme.

5.8. SedNet

SedNet²⁰³ is a European network aimed at incorporating sediment issues and knowledge into European strategies to support the achievement of a good environmental status and to develop new tools for contaminated sediment management. The network was set up in 2002 and funded by the EC DG-Research effort. Today, the network works within several working groups, including 'Education-Science-Policy Interfacing & Sediment Management Concepts', 'Sediments in Circular Economy', 'Sediment Quality' and 'Sediment Quantity'.

¹⁹⁹ <https://www.hamburg-port-authority.de/en/chainport>

²⁰⁰ <http://www.etp-alice.eu>

²⁰¹ Transparency Register number 006901422654-34

²⁰² Recognized by the European Commission as a European Technology Platform (ETP) in 2013. SWD (2013)272/F1 COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT STRATEGY FOR EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY PLATFORMS: ETP 2020

²⁰³ <https://sednet.org/>

5.9. Central Dredging Association (CEDA)

CEDA²⁰⁴ aims to be an established authority and the leading independent forum for the professional dredging community, and associated industries, in Europe, Africa and the Middle East. CEDA (2024) fosters and promotes the understanding and advancement of dredging to the wider community, while also regularly gives expert advice to government and international regulatory bodies. CEDA members are representative of consultancies, research and educational institutions, port authorities, government agencies, dredging contractors, designers and builders of dredging vessels, suppliers of ancillary equipment, and organizations providing a whole range of related services.

5.10. World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC)

The World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC)²⁰⁵ is a non-political and non-profit organisation established in 1885, with mission is to bring together international experts to issue high-ranking technical reports covering a wide range of topics related to sustainable waterborne transport infrastructure. PIANC provides many useful technical documentations, such as guidance for the beneficial use of dredged materials (Suedel et al., 2022)²⁰⁶.

5.11. International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR)

For the benefit of the Rhine and of all waters running into the Rhine, the members of the International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR)²⁰⁷ – Switzerland, France, Germany, Luxemburg, the Netherlands and the European Commission successfully co-operate with Austria, Liechtenstein and the Belgian region of Wallonia as well as Italy. Nine states and regions in the Rhine watershed closely co-operate in order to harmonize the many interests of use and protection in the Rhine area. Focal points of work are sustainable development of the Rhine, its alluvial areas and the good state of all waters in the watershed. One of the objectives of ICPR is to implement improvements such that dredged material may be deposited without causing any environmental harm.

5.12. European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)

In terms of monitoring extreme weather events, the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)²⁰⁸ is driving the digital transformation of ports by building and hosting innovative maritime information and monitoring systems that assure interoperability and compatibility among EU Member States. These digital tools help to simplify operations, minimise administrative costs, and improve the efficacy of the EU's maritime framework. Initiatives such as digitalizing flag State e-certification registries and promoting electronic certificates in port State control, which are encouraged by characteristics such as ship risk profile, allow for more efficient and focused inspections. Furthermore, technology such as earth observation for pollution detection, port inspection tools, and vessel traffic monitoring represent cutting-edge innovations that improve sector resilience and environmental stewardship. EMSA's efforts to promote cooperation and trust among member states through joint initiatives, best practice exchange, and collaborative frameworks have

²⁰⁴ <https://www.dredging.org/>

²⁰⁵ <https://www.pianc.org/>

²⁰⁶ <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/10.1061/9780784484401.011>

²⁰⁷ <https://www.iksr.org/en/>

²⁰⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX%3A52023DC0268>

a worldwide influence. EMSA improves national administrations' ability to manage maritime safety and environmental protection by rewriting key directives and offering specialised tools, training, and expert assistance. This comprehensive approach integrates digital innovations with collaborative efforts, ensuring that EU maritime ports remain resilient, safe, and capable of supporting sustainable operations amidst evolving challenges such as geopolitical shifts and global pandemics.

6. Related research projects

The following table (Table 3) presents other research projects, completed or on-going, that are relevant to the wider scope of the CLARION project. Table 3 uses as a starting point the corresponding Table 16 of Deliverable report D3.1 “Current State-of-the-art, Enablers, Barriers and Challenges”²⁰⁹ of the PIONEERS project, which is adapted and enriched with new projects.

Project	Port	Keywords
AEGIS ²¹⁰	Port of Aalborg, Vordingborg Port, Trondheim Port Authority	Marine automation, green intermodal systems
ANYWHERE ²¹¹		Extreme climate and weather events, early-warning, Pan-European multi-hazard platform
AUTOSHIP ²¹²	Norway	Automation, next gen port, supply chain, shortsea shipping transport
AVATAR ²¹³		Zero-emission, automated vessels, autonomous ship units
BCLink ²¹⁴	Port of Barcelona	Motorways of the Seas (MoS)
BIO-POLIS ²¹⁵		Climate Resilience, Water management, Urban Ecosystems
CarEsmatic ²¹⁶	Port of Barcelona	Motorways of the Seas (MoS), electric and hybrid vehicles
CHARIOT ²¹⁷		Privacy, Security and Safety (PSS) of IoT Systems
CIPROTECTION ²¹⁸		Safety and protection of Critical Infrastructure (CI), resilience of CI against multiple hazards, security of Widezones
CIRCUIT ²¹⁹		Circular construction approaches, regenerative cities, circular, smart, resilient, and sustainable transport infrastructures
CLEVER Cities ²²⁰		Nature-based solutions
Clinsh ²²¹	Port of Antwerp, North Sea Port	Greening measures, air quality
Core LNGas Hive ²²²	Port of Barcelona	LNG, RO/RO vessel, Straddle Carriers, clean energy

²⁰⁹ <https://pioneers-ports.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/State-of-the-Art-Gaps-and-Challenges-for-Green-Ports.pdf>

²¹⁰ <https://aegis.autonomous-ship.org/>

²¹¹ <http://anywhere-h2020.eu/>

²¹² <https://www.autoship-project.eu/>

²¹³ <https://northsearegion.eu/avatar/>

²¹⁴ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/bclink>

²¹⁵ <https://networknature.eu/ridb/biophilic-metropolis-holistic-model-urban-planning-and-building-climate-resilience>

²¹⁶ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/caresmatic>

²¹⁷ <https://www.chariotproject.eu/>

²¹⁸ <http://www.ciprotection.gr/index.php/en/>

²¹⁹ <https://www.circuit-project.eu/>

²²⁰ <https://clevercities.eu/>

²²¹ <https://www.clinsh.eu/>

²²² <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/core-lngas-hive>

Project	Port	Keywords
COREALIS ²²³	Port of Antwerp, Valencia Port, Port System Authority of Northern Tyrrhenian Sea	Cargo flow optimized, 5G, IoT, Energy assessment
Creators ²²⁴	Port of Barcelona	Smart energy, Community Energy Systems
DATAPORTS ²²⁵	Port of Valencia, Port of Thessaloniki	Data Platform, Cognitive Ports, AI, IoT, PCS
DISpATch ²²⁶		Digital twin, Synchro modal transport
DocksTheFuture ²²⁷		Digitalization, sustainability
Ealing ²²⁸	Port of Barcelona	Alternative fuels, Onshore Power Supply, Cold Ironing
ECCONET ²²⁹		Inland Waterway Transport (IWT), climate change, adaptation strategies
enerPort II ²³⁰	Port of Duisburg	Sustainability. Hydrogen, energy storage, renewable energy
ePcenter ²³¹	Port of Antwerp, Port of Montreal, Algeciras Port	AI driven logistic software solutions, new transport technologies, global supply chains, reduced environmental impact, Digital transformation, containers, connectivity
EWENT ²³²		Extreme weather impacts on European networks of transport
FENIX ²³³		Data sharing, Transport network
FORESEE ²³⁴		Resilient multimodal transport system, disruptive hazards
H2SHIPS ²³⁵	Amsterdam port authority	Hydrogen bunkering, vessels, hydrogen power and refuelling system
IMMERSE ²³⁶	Port of Antwerp	Sustainable management
iNGENIOUS ²³⁷		IoT, 5G
ISOLA ²³⁸		Ship security, automation
iWater ²³⁹		Integrated Storm Water Management

²²³ <https://www.corealis.eu/>

²²⁴ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/creators>

²²⁵ <https://dataports-project.eu/>

²²⁶ <https://vil.be/en/project/dispatch-digital-twin-for-synchromodal-transport/>

²²⁷ <https://www.docksthefuture.eu/>

²²⁸ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/ealing>

²²⁹ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/knowledge/adaptation-information/research-projects/econnet>

²³⁰ <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/europe-to-get-1st-climate-neutral-container-terminal-based-on-hydrogen-tech/>

²³¹ <https://epcenterproject.eu/>

²³² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/233919/reporting/de>

²³³ <https://fenix-network.eu/>

²³⁴ <https://foreseeproject.eu/>

²³⁵ <https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/h2ships-system-based-solutions-for-h2-fuelled-water-transport-in-north-west-europe/>

²³⁶ <https://northsearegion.eu/immerse/about/>

²³⁷ <https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/>

²³⁸ <https://isola-project.eu/>

²³⁹ <https://networknature.eu/ridb/integrated-storm-water-management>

Project	Port	Keywords
LNGHIVE2 Barcelona ²⁴⁰	Port of Barcelona	LNG bunker barge, reduction of polluting emissions in maritime transport
LOGIMATIC ²⁴¹	Port of Thessaloniki	Smart port, vehicle management, port vehicle automation
MAGPIE ²⁴²	Port of Rotterdam, Port of Siner, HAROPA Port, Fellow ports DeltaPort	Multimodal hubs, green energy containers, inland shipping, smart energy systems
MIRACA ²⁴³		Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment ,Critical Infrastructure, climate risk, extreme weather events
MiRO 2 ²⁴⁴	Port of Barcelona	Multimodal combined transport, interoperability, reduce environmental impact, carbon footprint and greenhouse gas emissions.
MOSES ²⁴⁵	Port of Valencia, Port Authority of Mykonos	System automation, supply chain optimization, sustainability
MOWE-IT ²⁴⁶		Adaptation strategies, risk reduction, transport performance, weather management
NOVIMOVE ²⁴⁷	Ports of Antwerp-Bruges, Port of Switzerland, Port of Rotterdam, Port of Duisburg	Inland shipping logistics system
PIF building Energy improvement ²⁴⁸	Port of Barcelona	Energy efficiency, renewable energy, photovoltaic systems
PILL ²⁴⁹	Port of Antwerp	Autonomous operations, digital twin, IoT
PIONEERS ²⁵⁰	Ports of Antwerp-Bruges, Barcelona, Venlo and Constanta	Clean energy production and supply, sustainable port design, modal shift and flows optimization, and digital transformation.
PIXEL ²⁵¹	Port of Piraeus, Thessaloniki Port Authority, Port Network Authority of the Eastern Adriatic Sea, Grand Port Maritime de Bordeaux	IoT, multimodal transport
PLANET ²⁵²	Port of Valencia (foundation), Comunidade Portuaria de Sines	Energy flows, synergies, reduced emission, Open ICT infrastructure,

²⁴⁰ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/Inghive2-barcelona>

²⁴¹ <https://logimatic-project.eu/>

²⁴² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036594>

²⁴³ <https://miraca-project.eu/>

²⁴⁴ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/miro-2>

²⁴⁵ <https://moses-h2020.eu/>

²⁴⁶ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/projects/management-of-weather-events-in-the-transport-system>

²⁴⁷ <https://novimove.eu/>

²⁴⁸ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/millora-energetica-pif>

²⁴⁹ <https://www.imec-int.com/en/pill>

²⁵⁰ <https://pioneers-ports.eu/>

²⁵¹ <https://pixel-ports.eu/>

²⁵² <https://www.h2020-planet.eu/>

Project	Port	Keywords
		Physical Internet, blockchain, synchro modality, IoT, Interconnected Corridor
PLATINE3 ²⁵³		Inland navigation, zero emissions, automation, clean energy hubs, fleets
PLOTO ²⁵⁴		Resilience of Inland Waterways against Climate Change
PortForward ²⁵⁵	Port of Vigo, Port de Baleares, Port System Authority of Northern Tyrrhenian Sea, Port of Kristiansand, Port of Magdeburg	Green ports, sustainable ports
PRECINCT ²⁵⁶		Cyber-physical security management, Digital Twins, Critical Infrastructure
RePort ²⁵⁷	Port of Barcelona	Reduce emissions, LNG, CNG
RESIST ²⁵⁸		Seamless transport operation to extreme events, predictive analytics, restoration of services/routes, communication of transport operators and users
RESOLUTE ²⁵⁹		Critical Infrastructure (CI) of the Urban Transport System (UTS)
Rhine Research Project POR I & II ²⁶⁰	Port of Rotterdam	Dredged material management, sustainable ports
SAFARI ²⁶¹	Ports of Dunkirk, Seville, Lisbon, Livorno, and Tripoli	Port operations, multi-modal transport, infrastructure resilience, extreme weather events
SANTANA ²⁶²	Port of Hamburg	Digital infrastructures, transport network
SCORE ²⁶³		Climate resilience, sea levels, coastal erosion, extreme weather events, smart technologies and nature-based solutions
Smart Ports Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (SPEED) ²⁶⁴	Port of Antwerp	Sustainable maritime transport, smart port, port logistics
Smartsediment ²⁶⁵	Port of Rotterdam, Port of Antwerp, Port of Hamburg, Port of Zeeland	Restoring the balance between biodiversity, soil and other functions in the Scheldt delta, smart sediment use.

²⁵³ <https://platina3.eu/what-we-do/>

²⁵⁴ <https://ploto-project.eu/>

²⁵⁵ <https://www.portforward-project.eu/>

²⁵⁶ <https://www.precinct.info/>

²⁵⁷ <https://www.portdebarcelona.cat/en/web/el-port/report>

²⁵⁸ <https://www.resistproject.eu/>

²⁵⁹ <https://www.resolute-eu.org/index.php>

²⁶⁰ [https://sednet.org/download/Handout_Rhine_Research_Project_II_\(English\).pdf](https://sednet.org/download/Handout_Rhine_Research_Project_II_(English).pdf)

²⁶¹ https://www.linkedin.com/company/safariports?trk=public_post-text

²⁶² <https://hamburg-news.hamburg/en/innovation-science/eur-15-million-digital-test-field-port-hamburg>

²⁶³ <https://score-eu-project.eu/>

²⁶⁴ <https://www.interreg2seas.eu/en>

²⁶⁵ <https://interregvianed.eu/smartsediment/over-ons>

Project	Port	Keywords
SOCORRO ²⁶⁶	Oostende, Vlissingen, Shoreham, Newhaven, Den Helder; canal Ghent-Terneuzen	Reduce economic impact, prediction of corrosion risks, sensor systems, LCA / LCCA
Sullied Sediments ²⁶⁷		Sediment assessment, management, removal and disposal
SURICATES ²⁶⁸	Port of Rotterdam	Sediment reuse for erosion and flood protection
SWARMPORT ²⁶⁹	Port of Rotterdam	Automation, nautical traffic management
Synchronet ²⁷⁰		Synchro modality, slow steaming, optimization, and simulation of flows
USAR ²⁷¹		Efficient Use of Resources and Materials
ZONeSEC ²⁷²		Protection of critical infrastructures, early detection and situation awareness technologies.

Table 3: Research projects relevant to CLARION

²⁶⁶ <https://www.socorro.eu/>

²⁶⁷ <https://northsearegion.eu/sullied-sediments/>

²⁶⁸ <https://vb.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/suricates-sediment-uses-as-resources-in-circular-and-territorial-economies/>

²⁶⁹ <https://www.tudelft.nl/2017/infrastructures/swarmport>

²⁷⁰ <https://www.synchronet.eu/>

²⁷¹ <https://www.interreg2seas.eu/en/usar>

²⁷² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/607292/reporting>

7. Key findings from the stakeholders' interviews

As described in the methodology section (1.1) of this report, the desk research was complemented by some semi-structured and unstructured interviews with key actors and stakeholders of three different ports of different scale and characteristics, within and outside the CLARION consortium, namely: Port of Rotterdam in The Netherlands, Port of Huelva in Spain and Port of Piraeus in Greece. The list of questions that were used as a basis for the semi-structured interviews can be found in Annex 3.

In order to gather specific needs and identify gaps and challenges for the Port of Rotterdam (PoR) in this field, an open discussion was arranged with Robbert Wolf, Nature and environmental advisor at the PoR and Alfred Roubos, expert from the PoR Development team.

The first feedback received from the experts was that nature in the Port of Rotterdam is well maintained and biodiversity is abundant, both on and in the water. The western part of the port is the reference for nature, however the eastern is more industrial and there is less room for biodiversity. Moreover, the low salinity levels limit the presence of certain species there, thus it could be interesting to explore innovations to promote and enhance biodiversity in that area.

Concerning the areas covered by the CLARION project, the expert provided his vision and relevant information that can be summarised as follows:

1. Artificial reefs have been already evaluated in the port and questions about the real the need of this biodiversity promotion measures arise, because as mentioned before, the biodiversity in the port is relevant and well preserved. On the other hand, if the biomimetic structures are made of concrete, there is an environmental impact behind, which is not positive. It could be interesting to explore possibilities to use shells or other natural materials to reduce carbon footprint and even maximise biodiversity promotion (for instance for shellfish, the best texture to attach to is another shell).
2. Monitoring systems: The Environment team in the Port Authority uses eDNA²⁷³ to monitor macrofauna and site's biodiversity. This tool provides the most comprehensive view available of the full spectrum of life as it uses traces of DNA to identify individual species from small samples of soil, sediment, water and air.
3. NbS in the port and hinterland: NbS in the port are well preserved and no particular needs were highlighted during the interview. In the case of NbS in the hinterland, they are managed by the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (in Dutch: Rijkswaterstaat - RWS), so it is not under the responsibility of the Port Authority.

Regarding the depollution of sediments, the experts highlighted that bioremediation techniques are known in the PoR. Other topics were also covered as part of the open discussion: The port and many other areas in the North Sea, have difficulties associated to the presence of the Japanese oyster, an invasive species that is seriously affecting the population of the flat oyster (native). Environmental associations are already undertaken actions to recover the population and indeed, there is a relevant population in Rotterdam, that could be used to support the recovery of the oyster in other areas. Tackling invasive species is important for the Port Authority, so it can be interesting to explore innovative monitoring solutions for this purpose.

According to Jaime Beltran Sanz (Business Development Manager) from the Port of Huelva, the most critical climate hazards that the Port will face in the years to come will be tsunamis/floods/storms, heatwaves and SLR. To address these challenges effectively, the Port has emergency and contingency

²⁷³ <https://www.naturemetrics.com/species-detection>

plans in place. It was highlighted that the Port of Huelva is involved in several green port initiatives such as:

- Use of renewable energy sources.
- Projects for the production, supply and consumption of alternative fuels such as green ammonia, methanol, bio-gnl and HVO.
- Projects of regeneration of the natural environment: restoration of degraded marshes
- Habitat and seabird recovery project through the beneficial use of dredging and bio-tools

When asked about the stakeholder community of the Port, and if communication, collaboration and information sharing among them can be considered sufficient when it comes to planning for resilience, the expert said that collaboration is crucial for the development of the Port of Huelva and its port community and that since 2006, biannual satisfaction surveys have been carried out with the port community and that there is also a historical archive, located in the Port Authority's Reception and Documentation Centre, which receives some 4,000 queries per year, providing a service for the dissemination and conservation of the Documentary Heritage, facilitating its access and consultation by interested parties.

Likewise, approximately 150 press releases are published annually to disseminate the main actions and projects carried out by the Port Authority of Huelva throughout the year, and the social media strategy of the Port is continuously improving. It was emphasized that the importance of the Port of Huelva as an engine of the provincial economy, its concern for the environmental management of port activity and the importance of the Port-City action programme have led the Port Authority of Huelva to belong to various associations of a technical or business nature, at regional (such as: HuelvaPort and Red Logística de Andalucía), national (such as: Technical Association of Ports and Coasts (ATPYC) and Iberian Association of Natural Gas for Mobility (GASNAM)), and at international level (such as: PIANC, IAPH and Docksthefuture). The Port of Huelva has been involved in several projects financed by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program in recent years and has obtained the 'Working with Nature' certification in 2024 from the World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC), for the management of its dredging, which in addition to maintaining the necessary draught to guarantee safe navigation, provides environmental benefits to the surroundings.

With respect to the hinterland of the Port of Huelva, the investments to improve rail connectivity with its hinterland are noteworthy. Spain's railway infrastructure administrator (ADIF: Administrador de Infraestructuras Ferroviarias), is now investing in the improvement of the two railway lines that connect Huelva with the Iberian Peninsula, making it possible to have two rail routes available for railway transport from the centre of the Iberian Peninsula to Huelva. At the meantime, the Port Authority of Huelva, together with the shipping companies that operate the Huelva-Canary Islands shipping lines, created the RUTA1400 maritime network to improve the operation and collaboration in the traffic between Huelva and the Canary Islands, with the Port of Huelva being currently the main port in terms of volume of goods with the Canary Islands.

Moreover, in Port of Huelva they believe that new industrial energy processes and energy flows in ports are going to be key in working towards a green, future-proof port, and that some of the barriers that need to be overcome of economic nature (the transition to renewable energy is expensive, therefore subsidies would be essential for companies in the port to achieve decarbonisation targets). In addition to that, cooperation among a large number of different actors with different backgrounds, objectives and aspirations and often competing interests, can be challenging as well.

Finally, on top of the above, Michael Kotras (IT Manager) from the Port of Piraeus indicated the importance of the implementation of the requirements of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and

the relevant emissions reporting based on the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). Most European ports fall under the category of organisations required to measure emissions as of January 1st, 2025, and report them along with the financial results at year end. Port “greening” is becoming a requirement both for regulatory compliance and competitiveness, especially if (or when) ports will be required to join the EU's Emissions Trading System similarly to their main clients, the shipping companies and operators.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable report, prepared in the context of the CLARION WP1, task T1.1, provides a thorough overview of the state-of-the-art in climate port resilience and safety, enriched with real world examples and best-practices from ports in Europe and beyond. By focusing on the ten thematic areas that are going to be investigated by the project's demonstration pilots, it sets the baseline for exploring innovative approaches while having a comprehensive understanding of existing conceptual advancements and practical applications. The overview demonstrated that although ports face, to a great extent, common challenges when it comes to climate change, one-size-fits-all approaches should not be the first choice when planning for resilience, and the unique characteristics of each port should be taken into account. Nevertheless, it is essential that new projects study the lessons learnt of previous initiatives and build on their gained knowledge; that is why a detailed inventory of completed and existed projects related to the CLARION scope is performed. The interviews with key stakeholders provided additional valuable insights on port communities' perspective and shed light to existing challenges and required actions. There is an increasingly growing volume of research on the role of digital innovations, such as digital twins, in enhancing climate resilience, but more real-world applications are needed to prove their effectiveness when used in port environments. The report can be useful to academics and researchers as well as policy-makers and practitioners, as it contributes to the ongoing societal discussions about the role of ports in the current era of transitions amidst the impacts of climate change, and can also help in raising public awareness about the increasing importance of developing climate adaptation and mitigation mechanisms.

9. Annexes

Annex 1

Table A1: Overview of recent scientific research (of the last 5 years: 2019-2024) in the field of climate change and ports.

	Reference	Year	Dimension (Infra/Oper/SC)	Disruption	Core	Methodology
1	Kievits, S. (2019). A framework for the impact assessment of low discharges on the performance of inland waterway transport, TU Delft	2019	Oper	Drought	Providing insight into the consequences of climate change-induced low discharges on the performance of IWT and to assist in making justified adaptation decisions	IWT performance model
2	Wood, G. D. A. (2019). Climate Delusion: Hurricane Sandy, Sea Level Rise, and 1840s Catastrophism. <i>Humanities</i> , 8(3), 131.	2019	General	Sea level Rise	Theorize catastrophe in the case study of Hurricane Sandy	Descriptive
3	Kontogianni, A., Damigos, D., Kyrtzoglou, T., Tourkolias, C., & Skourtos, M. (2019). Development of a composite climate change vulnerability index for small craft harbours. <i>Environmental Hazards</i> , 18(2), 173-190.	2019	Infra	Sea level Rise; Flooding	An integrated vulnerability index (VI) for small raft harbours, considering geophysical and socio-economic parameters	Descriptive
4	Asadabadi, A., & Miller-Hooks, E. (2020). Maritime port network resiliency and reliability through co-opetition. <i>Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review</i> , 137, 101916.	2020	SC	General	Assessing and improving the resilience and reliability of global port network	Stochastic Optimization
5	Verschuur, J., Koks, E. E., & Hall, J. W. (2020). Port disruptions due to natural disasters: Insights into port and logistics resilience. <i>Transportation research part D: transport and environment</i> , 85, 102393.	2020	Oper	General	Use of vessel tracking data to analyse past port disruptions due to natural disasters	AIS-based statistical analysis
6	Ryan-Henry, J., & Becker, A. (2020). Port stakeholder perceptions of Sandy impacts: A case study of Red Hook, New York. <i>Maritime Policy & Management</i> , 47(7), 885-902.	2020	Infra/Oper	Storm	Exploration of Hurricane Sandy storm impacts using evidence solicited from stakeholder representatives	Descriptive/Case study
7	van Dorsser, C., Vinke, F., Hekkenberg, R., & van Koningsveld, M. (2020). The effect of low water on loading capacity of inland ships. <i>European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research</i> , 20(3), 47-70.	2020	Oper	Drought	A general model to define the effect of low water constraints on the deadweight capacity and payload of inland ships	Mathematical Models

	Reference	Year	Dimension (Infra/Oper/SC)	Disruption	Core	Methodology
8	Morris, L. L. (2020). Stakeholder collaboration as a pathway to climate adaptation at coastal ports. <i>Maritime Policy & Management</i> , 47(7), 953-967.	2020	Infra/Oper	General	Overview of port climate adaptation approaches	Descriptive
9	León-Mateos, F., Sartal, A., López-Manuel, L., & Quintas, M. A. (2021). Adapting our sea ports to the challenges of climate change: Development and validation of a Port Resilience Index. <i>Marine Policy</i> , 130, 104573.	2021	SC	General	A port resilience index (PRI) considering all stakeholders to determine the level of operational resilience of port processes	Port resilience index
10	Mclean, E. L., & Becker, A. (2021). Advancing seaport resilience to natural hazards due to climate change: strategies to overcome decision making barriers. <i>Frontiers in Sustainability</i> , 2, 673630.	2021	Oper	General	Semi-structured interviews to respond to the question of how seaport decision makers perceive strategies to overcome the barriers to adaptation	Descriptive
11	Poo, M. C. P., Yang, Z., Dimitriu, D., Qu, Z., Jin, Z., & Feng, X. (2021). Climate change risk indicators (CCRI) for seaports in the United Kingdom. <i>Ocean & Coastal Management</i> , 205, 105580.	2021	Infra/Oper	General	A Climate Change Risk Indicator (CCRI) framework for climate risk assessment	Evidence Reasoning
12	Jarriel, K. (2021). Climate disaster and the resilience of local maritime networks: Two examples from the Aegean Bronze Age. <i>Quaternary International</i> , 597, 118-130.	2021	Infra	General	Addressing what effect two climate disasters had on small-world maritime networks in the Bronze Age Cyclades, and how the island inhabitants adapted	Descriptive
13	Ribeiro, A. S., Lopes, C. L., Sousa, M. C., Gomez-Gesteira, M., & Dias, J. M. (2021). Flooding conditions at Aveiro Port (Portugal) within the framework of projected climate change. <i>Journal of Marine Science and Engineering</i> , 9(6), 595.	2021	Infra	Flooding	Assessing the flood extent for Aveiro Port for historical, near future, and far future periods scenarios considering different return periods for the flood drivers, through numerical simulations of the ESL, wave regime, and riverine flows simultaneously.	Descriptive/Case study
14	Echendu, A. J. (2021). Relationship between urban planning and flooding in Port Harcourt city, Nigeria; insights from planning professionals. <i>Journal of Flood Risk Management</i> , 14(2), e12693.	2021	Infra	Flooding	Exploring how urban planning is linked to flooding in Port Harcourt	Descriptive/Case study
15	Moreno-Fernández, D., Zavala, M. A., Madrigal-González, J., & Seijo, F. (2021). Resilience as a moving target: An evaluation of last century management strategies in a dry-edge maritime pine ecosystem. <i>Forests</i> , 12(9), 1151.	2021	Infra/Oper	General	Evaluation of Last Century Management Strategies	Historical Data Analysis
16	Folkman, D., Gharehgozli, A., Mileski, J., & Galvao, C. B. (2021). Port resiliency and the effects of hurricanes on port	2021	Oper	Hurricanes	Simulate port operations before and after a hurricane	Simulation

	Reference	Year	Dimension (Infra/Oper/SC)	Disruption	Core	Methodology
	operations. <i>International Journal of Advanced Operations Management</i> , 13(4), 409-430.					
17	Izaguirre, C., Losada, I. J., Camus, P., Vigh, J. L., & Stenek, V. (2021). Climate change risk to global port operations. <i>Nature Climate Change</i> , 11(1), 14-20.	2021	Oper	General	Risk-modelling framework which risk is a function of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability to highlight the contribution of climate change to risk in port operations in the absence of adaptation	Data analysis
18	Zhou, C., Xu, J., Miller-Hooks, E., Zhou, W., Chen, C. H., Lee, L. H., & Li, H. (2021). Analytics with digital-twinning: A decision support system for maintaining a resilient port. <i>Decision Support Systems</i> , 143, 113496.	2021	Infra	General	A DSS with digital twinning-based resilience analysis for port resilience computation and updating which assesses the resilience of a port under possible disruptive events given its design, operations, and potential pre-defined post-event recovery actions to mitigate the impact of the disruption.	Digital Twinning
19	Abdelhafez, M. A., Ellingwood, B., & Mahmoud, H. (2021). Vulnerability of seaports to hurricanes and sea level rise in a changing climate: A case study for mobile, AL. <i>Coastal Engineering</i> , 167, 103884.	2021	Infra/Oper	Sea level Rise; Hurricanes	Review and appraisal of the potential impact of hurricanes in North America on a typical coastal seaport community	Descriptive/Case study
20	Wienk, T. (2021). Evaluation of the resilience of inland waterway transport to increasing periods of low flow, following a Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathway approach, TU Delft	2021	Oper	Drought	Developing an adaptive planning that can cope with deep uncertainties that a decision-maker has in face of IWT drought	Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathway
21	Verschuur, J., Pant, R., Koks, E., & Hall, J. (2022). A systemic risk framework to improve the resilience of port and supply-chain networks to natural hazards. <i>Maritime Economics & Logistics</i> , 1-18.	2022	SC	General	A systemic risk framework for different networks interconnected through ports, and describe the state-of-the-art risk modelling approaches to quantify systemic risks	Risk Analysis
22	da Veiga Lima, F. A., & de Souza, D. C. (2022). Climate change, seaports, and coastal management in Brazil: An overview of the policy framework. <i>Regional Studies in Marine Science</i> , 52, 102365.	2022	Infra	General	Identifying and evaluating the extent to which the climate change topic is addressed by the port planning, coastal management, and climate adaptation policies of Brazil.	Descriptive/Case study
23	Wan, C., Tao, J., Yang, Z., & Zhang, D. (2022). Evaluating recovery strategies for the disruptions in liner shipping networks: a resilience approach. <i>The international journal of logistics management</i> , 33(2), 389-409.	2022	Oper	General	Establishing a novel risk-based resilience framework to measure the effectiveness of different recovery strategies for the disruptions in LSNs in a quantitative manner.	Resilience-cost analysis
24	Li, W., Asadabadi, A., & Miller-Hooks, E. (2022). Enhancing resilience through port coalitions in maritime freight	2022	SC	General	Improving the resilience of individual ports, strategies involving capacity sharing and protective cross-port investments through coalition formation	Game theory

	Reference	Year	Dimension (Infra/Oper/SC)	Disruption	Core	Methodology
	networks. <i>Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice</i> , 157, 1-23.					
25	Balakrishnan, S., Lim, T., & Zhang, Z. (2022). A methodology for evaluating the economic risks of hurricane-related disruptions to port operations. <i>Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice</i> , 162, 58-79.	2022	Infra	Hurricanes	A framework and methodology to analyse the economic risks of hurricane-related shutdowns using hurricane- and port-related determinants	Risk Analysis
26	Vinke, F., van Koningsveld, M., van Dorsser, C., Baart, F., Van Gelder, P., & Vellinga, T. (2022). Cascading effects of sustained low water on inland shipping. <i>Climate Risk Management</i> , 35, 100400.	2022	SC	Drought	Suggesting a method to explicitly include the cascading effects of low discharge events in climate risk assessments of waterborne supply chain performance, at system level	Simulation
27	Allen, T. R., McLeod, G., & Hutt, S. (2022). Sea level rise exposure assessment of US East Coast cargo container terminals. <i>Maritime Policy & Management</i> , 49(4), 577-599.	2022	Infra/Oper	Sea level Rise	A methodology for major container port terminals to advance a screening approach to sea level rise, identify exposure to terminals and associated surface transportation, and enable comparative assessment	Data analysis
28	Liu, Q., Yang, Y., Ng, A. K., & Jiang, C. (2023). An analysis on the resilience of the European port network. <i>Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice</i> , 175, 103778.	2023	Oper	General	Resilience measures based on topological indices from graph theory to measure three essential aspects of the network resilience, connection extent, connection efficiency, and connection scale	Data analysis, graph theory
29	Islam, S., Goerlandt, F., Sakalayan, Q. M. H., Shi, Y., & Venkatesh, V. G. (2023). Developing a "Disaster Scenario" to prepare for the possibility of disruptions to maritime transportation serving coastal communities of Vancouver Island. <i>Marine Policy</i> , 150, 105531.	2023	Oper	General	A catastrophe scenario following consultations with a marine stakeholder and a marine geologist, and its viability	Scenario-based Risk Analysis
30	Bal, F., & Vleugel, J. M. (2023). Towards climate resilient freight transport in Europe. <i>International Journal of Transport Development and Integration</i> , 7(2).	2023	Oper	Drought	It is dealing with the question: If the Rhine becomes locally inaccessible, could railways (temporarily) play a larger role in freight transport?	Simulation
31	Tsaimou, C. N., Sartampakos, P., & Tsoukala, V. K. (2023). UAV-driven approach for assisting structural health monitoring of port infrastructure. <i>Structure and Infrastructure Engineering</i> , 1-20.	2023	Infra	General	Investigating the capabilities of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) monitoring program to advance current SHM practices for port infrastructure	Data Analysis
32	Vinke, F., & Turpijn, B. (2024). Inland shipping response to discharge extremes—A 10 years case study of the Rhine. <i>Climate Risk Management</i> , 43, 100578.	2023	Oper	Drought	Analysing ten years of IVS and discharge data, for the period between 2010 and 2020, revealing in detail for the	Data analysis

	Reference	Year	Dimension (Infra/Oper/SC)	Disruption	Core	Methodology
					first time how discharge levels and vessel deployment are related	
33	Shi, J., Chen, J., Xu, L., Di, Z., & Qu, Q. (2023). Improving the resilience of maritime supply chains: The integration of ports and inland transporters in duopoly markets. <i>Frontiers of Engineering Management</i> , 10(1), 51-66.	2023	SC	General	Investigating the impact of cooperation between ports and inland logistics providers and government regulation on the maritime supply chain by comparing members' optimal pricing and overall social welfare	Game theory
34	Sharaan, M., Ibrahim, M. G., Moubarak, H., ElKut, A. E., Romya, A. A., Hamouda, M., & Iskander, M. (2024). A Qualitative Analysis of Climate Impacts on Egyptian Ports. <i>Sustainability</i> , 16(3), 1015.	2024	Infra	General	Examining how the port authorities perceive and respond to climate hazards in one of the most important and largest commercial Egyptian ports	Descriptive
35	Grant, R., Rhode-Barbarigos, L., Roy, S. S., Britton, L., Li, C., Rowe, A., & Bello, M. (2024). No port stands alone: PortMiami and the resilience of its Caribbean and Mesoamerican maritime network. <i>Maritime Economics & Logistics</i> , 1-24.	2024	SC	General	Exploring PortMiami's regional maritime network, and their potential impact on the port's long-term resilience and growth potential.	Data analysis
36	Poo, M. C. P., & Yang, Z. (2024). Optimising the resilience of shipping networks to climate vulnerability. <i>Maritime Policy & Management</i> , 51(1), 15-34.	2024	Oper	General	Assessing the global shipping network focusing on climate resilience, combining climate risk indicators, centrality analysis, and ship routing optimisation	Centrality analysis, optimization
37	Bakker, F. P., & van Koningsveld, M. Tool to evaluate countermeasures at locks to limit freshwater losses and saltwater intrusion while minimizing waiting times for shipping, <i>35th PIANC World Congress</i> , 29 April - 3 May 2024, Cape Town, South Africa	2024	Infra	Drought	Presenting a method to analyse lock operations and saltwater intrusion, combining a meso-scale logistical model with a semi-empirical hydrodynamic model of a lock	Simulation
38	Brooke, J., Giovando, J., Dahl, T. A., Joyner, B., & Herbert, L. (2024, January). Port and inland waterway design and operation in the face of climate change uncertainty. In <i>Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Civil Engineering</i> (Vol. 177, No. 5, pp. 37-49). Emerald Publishing Limited.	2024	Infra/Oper	Several	A scenario-based approach can be used to identify an appropriate range of projections for assessing risks and designing structures	Descriptive

Annex 2

Table B1: Existing work on resilience of connected inland waterways, roads and railways infrastructure

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions
<p>Panteia (2021) Achterlandkosten – in Dutch.</p> <p>Report itself is confidential – assignment done for PoR in 2021</p>	<p>Hinterland Rotterdam shrinks under conditions of low water: barging costs increase strongly and rail and (mainly) road become cheaper for destinations around the Rhine corridor.</p> <p>Also, it may lead to port shift: traffic by road via Antwerp is shorter distance to Germany.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div data-bbox="546 804 1030 1321"> <p style="font-size: small;">Verschil Rotterdam - overige havens 2018</p> </div> </div>	<p>How to avoid steep cost increases for IWT due to low water/drought?</p> <p>How much of the freight transport demand can still be accommodated?</p> <p>What measures are most effective to maintain as much transportation capacity as possible?</p>

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions
Deltares (2020) Water level prediction – assignment for Rijkswaterstaat	<p>Whereas until then the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water management (Rijkswaterstaat) published expected water levels for (only) 48 hours ahead, the Deltares analysis showed that a longer term prediction up to 6 weeks would be possible – however with reduced levels of reliability for further ahead futures.</p> <p>On this basis, Rijkswaterstaat has decided that while their ‘normal’ water level prediction is maintained at 48 hours (see waterinfo.rws.nl), as a separate service they now publish a 2-weeks forecast for 2 locations in NL, one for the Rhine in Lobith and one for the Maas.</p>	
BCI (2023) Multimodal Resilience on the Rhine Corridor (assignment for Topsector Logistiek)	<p>Analysis of changes in supply and demand for IWT during periods of low water. Impact varies between different market segments. For some markets, delivery certainty is more important (worth more – willingness to pay) than for other markets.</p> <p>Inventory of possible logistics measures that can be taken.</p>	<p>Initial elaboration made on possible short and long term actions that market and government could take. However, their implementation requires further research, according to the report.</p>
TRANS-2 (ongoing TKI project led by Deltares)	<p>Project includes a range of working sessions with stakeholders and its findings can feed into the CLARION project.</p>	
Workshops with operators (2019) organized by PoR	<p>Following urgent problems faced in 2018 in the logistics to/from Rotterdam, PoR called stakeholders at the table from the dry and liquid bulk segment to discuss how the situation was dealt with and what kind of missing needs were observed.</p> <p>Subsequent conclusion was that more frequent and regular information exchange between logistics chain parties is important and should be set-up already prior to low water actually taking place.</p> <p>This conclusion was brought forward to Rijkswaterstaat, and a regular ‘Drought knowledge exchange’ meeting cycle was set-up, which can be ‘sleeping’ during winter and activated during summer. This structure still stands.</p>	
RWS (2022) Bepaling OLR Rijntakken (in Dutch)	<p>Report calculating which agreed lowest water levels will be applicable for the coming 10 years.</p>	

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions																																								
BASF (2020) newspaper article	BASF wappnet sich für Niedrigwasserphasen																																									
Ecorys (2019) kosten en baten laagwater scheepvaart	Economic analysis on behalf of Rijkswaterstaat	Only looks at NL side, disregards German cost impacts. This was solved in subsequent EUR study (see next)																																								
EUR Economische impact laagwater (2020)	<p>Following the Ecorys study, which disregarded international impacts, KBN assigned Erasmus University to redo the analysis including impacts across the border of NL.</p> <p>Conclusion: costs of 2018 low water were up to €3 billion mainly for industries in Germany.</p> <p><i>Tabel 1: financiële impact Nederland en Duitsland laagwater</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th></th> <th>Nederland</th> <th>Duitsland</th> <th>Totaal</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="3">Financiële impact sector binnenvaart</td> <td>Netto omzetstijging:</td> <td>+ 378 miljoen euro</td> <td>+ 95 miljoen euro</td> <td>+ 473 miljoen euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Extra kosten:</td> <td>- 302 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 76 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 378 miljoen euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nettowinst:</td> <td>+ 76 miljoen euro</td> <td>+ 19 miljoen euro</td> <td>+ 95 miljoen euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="4">Financiële impact verladere</td> <td>Transportkosten:</td> <td>- 245 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 243 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 488 miljoen euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Productievermindering</td> <td>- 60 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 2,1 miljard euro</td> <td>- 2,2 miljard euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Voorraadaanvulling</td> <td>- 66 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 65 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 131 miljoen euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Totale negatieve impact</td> <td>- 371 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 2,4 miljard euro</td> <td>- 2,8 miljard euro</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Totale financiële impact</td> <td></td> <td>- 295 miljoen euro</td> <td>- 2,4 miljard euro</td> <td>- 2,7 miljard euro</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Nederland	Duitsland	Totaal	Financiële impact sector binnenvaart	Netto omzetstijging:	+ 378 miljoen euro	+ 95 miljoen euro	+ 473 miljoen euro	Extra kosten:	- 302 miljoen euro	- 76 miljoen euro	- 378 miljoen euro	Nettowinst:	+ 76 miljoen euro	+ 19 miljoen euro	+ 95 miljoen euro	Financiële impact verladere	Transportkosten:	- 245 miljoen euro	- 243 miljoen euro	- 488 miljoen euro	Productievermindering	- 60 miljoen euro	- 2,1 miljard euro	- 2,2 miljard euro	Voorraadaanvulling	- 66 miljoen euro	- 65 miljoen euro	- 131 miljoen euro	Totale negatieve impact	- 371 miljoen euro	- 2,4 miljard euro	- 2,8 miljard euro	Totale financiële impact		- 295 miljoen euro	- 2,4 miljard euro	- 2,7 miljard euro	Report only looked at short term economic losses. Question remains what the long term impact would be e.g. if industries would decide to reallocate to other places (outside Europe?) leaving a loss of economic value and a loss of employment.
		Nederland	Duitsland	Totaal																																						
Financiële impact sector binnenvaart	Netto omzetstijging:	+ 378 miljoen euro	+ 95 miljoen euro	+ 473 miljoen euro																																						
	Extra kosten:	- 302 miljoen euro	- 76 miljoen euro	- 378 miljoen euro																																						
	Nettowinst:	+ 76 miljoen euro	+ 19 miljoen euro	+ 95 miljoen euro																																						
Financiële impact verladere	Transportkosten:	- 245 miljoen euro	- 243 miljoen euro	- 488 miljoen euro																																						
	Productievermindering	- 60 miljoen euro	- 2,1 miljard euro	- 2,2 miljard euro																																						
	Voorraadaanvulling	- 66 miljoen euro	- 65 miljoen euro	- 131 miljoen euro																																						
	Totale negatieve impact	- 371 miljoen euro	- 2,4 miljard euro	- 2,8 miljard euro																																						
Totale financiële impact		- 295 miljoen euro	- 2,4 miljard euro	- 2,7 miljard euro																																						
CCR workshop low water (November 2019 in Bonn) and subsequent follow-up sessions	<p>With follow-up paper ‘Act Now’.</p> <p>“Act now!” on low water and effects on Rhine navigation (ccr-zkr.org)</p> <p>Various follow-up workshops, amongst others one on price formation in the various subsectors. Reports/notes available through CCNR website.</p>	CCR puts the key problems on the agenda. However, decision making is with the Member States, currently lacking funds for infrastructure investments. Therefore CLARION research is important to show the added value and to help prioritise.																																								
TNO (2020) rail as a contingency mode for	Research into the possibility of the rail sector to take over transport demand when IWT is limited due to low water. Main conclusions that	How to take advance measures to make sure that once low water																																								

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions
<p>barge in situations of low water levels on the Rhine (assignment for PoR)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity to increase volumes by rail is limited - Procedures to add train services take long (ca. 6 weeks), so flexibility from an operational perspective is limited. 	<p>occurs, all arrangements are in place to scale up the actual use of rail.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Required long term investments - Business case of measures
<p>Kriedel (2019) Low water levels on the Rhine and their economic impact. Smart Rivers conference</p>	<p>Presentation by Norbert Kriedel, administrator for statistics and market observation with the Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine (CCNR), on the economic impacts observed following the 2018 drought. Showing the historical perspective (low water has happened before and even worse) and the economic impacts (vulnerability has strongly increase since the 1980s)</p>	<p>Suggestions done for possible measures e.g. new or modified vessel design</p>
<p>NOVIMOVE (EU project 2019-2024)</p>	<p>Horizon Europe project 2019-2024 (completed in May 2024) in which a range of concepts have been developed and researched into “Novel inland waterway transport concepts for moving freight effectively”.</p> <p>Amongst others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logistics design, e.g. floating hub to bundle and reorganize containers in seaports. - Buoyancy increasing measures to connect to ships passing low water sections - Serious Game <p>NOVIMOVE – Smart & sustainable waterways</p> <p>All deliverables available through TU Delft who was the lead partner.</p>	<p>Findings seem to fit perfectly in the CLARION scope of work.</p>
<p>Deltares (2022) Robust hinterland connections in times of drought and heat</p>	<p>Report by Deltares, MARIN and TNO for Rijkswaterstaat. NWO project.</p> <p>Inventory study concluding three avenues for further research:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. River flow information and expectations 2. Adaptation measures (fleet, waterways and ports, logistics) 3. Broader context: role in societal challenges of energy supply, circularity, digitization etc. 	<p>Proposed research agenda.</p>

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions
ICBR (2019) Klimawandel- anpassungsstrategie für die IFGE Rhein	Report by the International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (in German) Giving governance suggestions on how to prepare for future high and low water situations and management plans to deal with them. Also ideas on how to involve NGO's, CCR and other stakeholders in the process.	
Twynstra (2020) Handelingsperspectieven droogte IJssel en Twentekanalen (in Dutch)	Study for the Province of Overijssel in the Netherlands. The IJssel river (tributary of the Rhine), proved to be very vulnerable to drought – even more than the Rhine/Waal itself. Because of its narrow bed and many curves, navigation is hampered severely even under slight drought conditions. The Twentekanaal is connected to the IJssel via locks and is the only waterway access to industrial locations in this part of NL. Water limitations will affect lock availability and thus block access to the canal. The study advised four angles: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More robust logistics chains 2. Improve facilities along the fairway 3. Strengthen the communications network between stakeholders 4. Investigate possible measures into the river system itself 	Some the work is now taken up from the University of Twente research on resilience. Twente researchers make transport chains more reliable using a 'digital twin' (utwente.nl)
Deltares et al. (2020-2) Digital Twin Vaarwegen – Smartport funded assignment	Pilot study to develop a Digital Twin of the (Dutch) Rhine and tributaries, using data from two private barge operators (Danser and NPRC) and developing scenarios to evaluate optimal fleet assignment. digitaltwin-waterway (deploy-preview-32-digitwin-waterways.netlify.app)	Results of this work are taken on board in CLARION
RWS (2022) Klimaatbestendige Netwerken (in Dutch)	Rijkswaterstaat evaluates the climate robustness of its infrastructure networks every six years. For waterways, a stress test was done in 2022. Separate reports were made related to drought, heat and high water. The report is a basis for RWS's infrastructure management plans and for prioritizing its investments.	

Report/source	Main findings	Remaining research questions
Frederik Vinke, various research papers	PhD student at TU Delft, assignment co-funded by SmartPort. Research into the impacts of climate change on IWT flows, and the feasibility of possible measures both on waterway system and fleet.	
Van Dorsser (2015) Very long term scenario's	PhD dissertation on the very long (2100) future of IWT.	

Annex 3

Questions used for the semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and key – actors

1. In your opinion, which are the three most critical climate hazards that Port X is currently facing or will face in the years to come?
2. How is Port X preparing to address these challenges? Please name any measures or approaches currently in place that aim at enhancing resilience and overcoming these challenges.
3. Are there any “green port” initiatives in which Port X is involved?
4. What about the stakeholder community of the port? Do you consider that the communication, collaboration and information sharing among them is sufficient when it comes to planning for resilience?
5. Is Port X involved in any national or EU projects around the topic of green or/and resilient ports?
6. Would you say that any actions taken towards enhancing port resilience so far, focus more on port infrastructure, on (hinterland) transport, or on both? Please provide specific examples.
7. Are you aware of any best-practices that Port X or any other EU port is applying in one or more of the following areas?
 - Quay walls
 - Infrastructure corrosion
 - Shore tension for RO/RO and CON/RO terminals
 - Flood impact control
 - Dredged sediment reuse
 - Nature Based Solutions
 - Resilience of connected inland waterways, roads and railways infrastructure
 - Extreme weather forecasting
 - Cadastral measurements and inland water level forecasting
 - Control systems for extreme weather events
8. What do you think is the most important characteristic of a green, future-proof Port?
9. What challenges/barriers need to be overcome when it comes to the successful application of policies and measures towards resilient ports?
10. According to you, which are the key success factors that can bring a port in the forefront of the sustainable transition?